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**UZBEKISTAN-KOREA RELATIONS:
PAST, PRESENT, AND PERSPECTIVES
IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL
CHALLENGES**

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The seminar aimed to analyze the relationship between Uzbekistan and Korea, focusing on political, economic, social, and cultural aspects. The goal was to explore strategies for strengthening the ties between the two nations, reflecting on their past and present while envisioning the future of their relationship. Through these discussions, the organizers sought to deepen understanding of the diverse and complex nature of Uzbek-Korean relations. The workshop’s outcomes aim to enhance political, economic, social, and cultural exchanges, laying the groundwork for continued, multifaceted development between the two countries.

This collection is intended for policymakers, professors, graduate students, undergraduates, and anyone interested in the dynamics of Uzbek-Korean relations.

Edited by Valeriy S. Khan

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**GREETINGS FROM OH NAM-HYUN,
THE PRESIDENT OF THE PEACEFUL UNIFICATION
ADVISORY COUNCIL'S CENTRAL ASIA CHAPTER
UNDER THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF
KOREA**

Despite everyone's hectic schedules, I would like to express my heartfelt congratulations on the opening of today's seminar on the topic of Uzbekistan-Korea Relations: Past, Present, and Perspectives in the Context of Global Challenges.

This seminar brings together the best experts from Uzbekistan and Korea to develop realistic and practical solutions for advancing the development and progress of both countries. I would like to express my gratitude to the professors, researchers, citizens, university students, and distinguished guests who have attended despite the cold weather. My special thanks go to the Vice-Rector of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy A. Umarov and the officials from the Korea Foundation who organized this event.

As we all know, Uzbekistan is renowned as the central hub of the Silk Road. It is said that the world is connected by the Silk Road and that world civilizations originated from it. Uzbekistan remains one of the most creative and dynamic countries in the world.

In the past, our ancestors from the Silla Kingdom used Uzbekistan as a gateway for trade with the West. Furthermore, 170,000 of our compatriots, with a 160-year history of

immigration, have settled here. Many companies, including Daewoo Motors, have also entered the region and are working in collaboration with Uzbekistan. In addition, more than 170,000 Uzbek citizens currently reside in Korea, both officially and unofficially. At least 500,000 people have direct or indirect ties with Korea, making Uzbekistan a close partner nation.

Thus, regardless of the past or present, our future has always been deeply interconnected, and we will continue to build and expand this relationship.

I am confident that Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea, with their distinct historical, cultural, geographical, and economic values, will demonstrate their ability to achieve mutual success and development.

In June, President Yoon Seok-yeol of the Republic of Korea made a state visit to three Central Asian countries and announced the K-Silk Road Initiative, a new vision for future cooperation between Korea and Central Asia. I believe that by fostering friendly and cooperative relations in politics, diplomacy, culture, and the economy, we have laid the foundation for shared prosperity between the Republic of Korea and Uzbekistan. This is particularly significant in today's rapidly changing international landscape and during a time of uncertainty about the future.

In this context, the seminar being held today is a meaningful program that allows us to reflect on the various policies promoting exchange between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea and to consider the direction in which the two countries should move forward. The participation of top experts in this seminar will enhance its value, ensuring productive discussions and outcomes.

I hope that the various topics and policies discussed here will serve as guidelines and milestones to respond to the changing times across all sectors of exchange between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea, including the economy, culture, and diplomacy.

Finally, I would like to thank all the participants of this seminar, the Vice Rector of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy, and the Korea Foundation for organizing this event. I wish good health to all of you in attendance.

UZBEK-KOREAN RELATIONS. GENERAL OVERVIEW. KOREAN DIASPORA

Valeriy S. Khan, Dr. Sc., PhD
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Head of the Project

Once, in the distant 7th century, envoys from the no less distant country of Koguryo, located on the eastern margins of Asia and washed by the waves of the Pacific Ocean, having traveled thousands of kilometers, arrived at the palace of the ruler of Samarkand, which was depicted on the frescoes of Afrasiab that have survived to our days. Subsequently, these ties were interrupted for many centuries. However, in the era of globalization, the movement of people and capital has acquired such a scale that dialogue and even close communication between once-distant countries is becoming the norm. Furthermore, new communication systems such as high-speed transportation, the internet, and mobile phones have compressed space and time to such an extent that today people from different continents can communicate as if time and space did not exist.

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea are linked by strategic partnership relations. And it is quite natural that the interest of the two countries' peoples in each other is growing before our eyes. The Republic of Korea is one of the largest investors in the economy of Uzbekistan. Thousands of Koreans come to Uzbekistan, and thousands of Uzbeks come to Korea for business, work, study, and just

rest; Koreans are beginning to speak Uzbek and Russian, and Uzbeks are beginning to speak Korean.

Historical relations. Korean Diaspora

The prehistory of relations between the Korean and Central Asian peoples goes back to ancient times. Some areas of the region, according to modern scientific understanding, played a role in the genesis of the Korean ethnos. The first documented fact of contacts between Korea and Central Asia is the preserved wall painting of Afrosiab in Samarkand, which depicts two Korean ambassadors at the reception of the Samarkand ruler, whose stay dates back to the 7th century. It is also known that the Korean monk Hecho traveled through Central Asia in the 8th century. In the battle of Talas (751) between the Arabs and the Chinese, the Chinese troops were commanded by Korean general Ko Seong-ji, a descendant of Ko Sa-gye, a warrior from Koguryo captured by the Chinese. Korean scholars believe that the stone sculptures in front of the tomb of Hengdok Wang (Silla, 9th century) are statues of Central Asians.

After the beginning of Korean immigration in the second half of the XIX century, the first Koreans (three people) appeared in the territory of modern Uzbekistan, which was recorded by the First General Census of the Russian Empire in 1897. The first All-Union census of 1926 recorded 36 Koreans in the Uzbek SSR.

In the same years, the first attempt of Koreans living in Central Asia to establish their organization was carried out. Thus, in 1921, a Korean section was created in the Commissariat for Nationalities of the Turkestan Republic. On August

26, 1924, the Union of Koreans of the Turkestan Republic was registered in the NKVD of the Turkestan Republic with 28 members. At the re-registration in February 1926, 33 people were listed in the Union's lists.

In 1937, more than 170,000 Koreans were forcibly relocated from the Russian Far East to Central Asia—Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan—by the Stalin-Molotov decree. 74,500 people arrived in Uzbekistan. During this difficult time, the Uzbek people extended a helping hand to the Koreans. In Uzbekistan, as of November 15, 1938, 48 independent Korean collective farms (5,301 households) were established. 5,145 farms were added to 211 local collective and state farms.

Before Stalin's death, there were no relations between Uzbekistan and the Korean peninsula. In the 60s-70s, there were some relations, first of all in the field of culture, with the DPRK. After the collapse of the USSR, diplomatic relations were established with the Republic of Korea. Today, the numerous Korean diaspora plays an important role in supporting friendly relations between our states and further rapprochement of our peoples. This Diaspora is the largest in the CIS (about 200 thousand people) and the fourth largest globally. In 2022, the 85th anniversary of Korean residence in Uzbekistan has been widely celebrated in our country.

The Korean diaspora is an integral part of the multi-ethnic people of Uzbekistan and traditionally takes an active part in all social and cultural events held in the country. Uzbekistan highly appreciates the contribution of Koreans to the country's socio-economic development—building up the country's industrial and agricultural potential and progress in science, education, health care, and other areas. In the twentieth century, more than 130 Koreans of Uzbeki-

stan were awarded the title “Hero of Labor” for their outstanding achievements in agriculture. Korean collective farmers achieved high yields not only in traditional crops (rice, legumes, etc.) but also in cotton growing. Koreans also achieved record yields of wheat, sugar beets, potatoes, kenaf, onions, melons, etc. Famous agricultural organizers such as Kim Peng Hwa and Hwang Man Geum have become legends.

In recognition of the organizational abilities of Koreans in the agricultural sector, dozens of collective and state farms in the Central Asian republics were entrusted to Koreans to run. Koreans also held high positions in agriculture at the district, regional, republican, and all-Union levels. These are such high positions as Chairman of the State Committee on Fisheries of Uzbekistan (H. T. Ten), Deputy Minister of Bread Products of Uzbekistan (N. D. Ten), Deputy Minister of Fruit and Vegetable Farming of Uzbekistan (H. T. Ten), Chairman of the Republican Beekeeping Association of Uzbekistan (M. I. Yun), Head of Grain Crops Department of the Ministry of Agriculture of Karakalpakstan (N. N. Tyan) and others.

Koreans have achieved impressive results not only in agriculture, but they have created a serious layer in other branches of the economy, science, culture, and sports. 283 representatives of the Korean Diaspora have been honored with high state awards and titles, and many of them enjoy great authority in our society. Among the Koreans of Central Asia, there are or were:

- deputies and members of the government (Deputy Prime Minister, ministers and deputy ministers, deputies of the Lower and Upper Chambers of the Oliy Majlis);
- members of the Academies of Sciences, rectors and vice-rectors, deans and heads of departments of higher education

institutions; directors, heads of departments and sectors of research institutes and NGOs);

- heads of large industrial, financial and agricultural enterprises; national airlines, and banks;

- famous sportsmen (prize-winners of Olympic Games, world and European championships, championships of the USSR and CIS countries, senior coaches of national teams, heads of associations in various sports);

- famous internationally recognized writers, composers, artists, entertainers, opera and ballet dancers, etc.

These are:

- Hero of Uzbekistan, director of the “Mehribonlik House” in Khiva, Vera Pak;

- Minister of Preschool Education, Senator Agrippina Shin;

- Senator Valery Tyan;

- Ambassador of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Republic of Korea Vitaly Fen;

- Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of Oliy Majlis, chairman of the Association of Korean Cultural Centers of Uzbekistan Victor Pak;

- World Cup winner (boxing) Vladimir Shin;

- Academician of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan, painter Nikolai Shin;

- Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Vladimir Kim; in general, in Uzbekistan, Koreans have defended more than 300 Dr. Sc. and Ph.D. dissertations;

- Honored Artists of Uzbekistan, singers Galina Shin and Zoya Tsoi, and many others.

Korean media (the newspaper “Koryo Shinmun”, the tele-

vision program “Chinsen” and the Internet portal “Koryo Saram”), exhibitions, concerts, festivals, tours of creative groups in Uzbekistan and abroad, scientific conferences, and various sports competitions among young people are organized in the country.

The Association of Korean Cultural Centers of Uzbekistan operates in Uzbekistan with an extensive network of branches.

The Korean International Health Fund, in cooperation with the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Korea, has built and maintains the “Ariran” nursing home (Tashkent province) for elderly Koreans in need in Uzbekistan.

The Koreans of Uzbekistan today form a large diaspora in Korea (more than 100,000). Once for them, living in the USSR, and even during the years of independence, Korea was their historical homeland. But if they have been living there for 15-20 years, their children go to kindergartens and schools, what is their historical homeland for those born in Uzbekistan and now living in Korea?

22 years ago I introduced the concept of “globalization of ethnicity”, one of the manifestations of which is the formation of meta-nations – global associations along ethnic lines: nation-state plus diasporas.

Jews, Armenians, Chinese, Russians, Kazakhs, and so on. The Korean meta-nation is gradually forming. And one of its parts is the Koreans of Uzbekistan.

Is the diaspora factor taken into account in the relations between Korea and Uzbekistan? There is also the Uzbek diaspora in Korea. It is necessary to establish a dialog with Uzbek citizens in Korea as part of the policy of constructing the Uzbek meta-nation.

After the establishment of diplomatic relations

Diplomatic relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea were officially established on January 29, 1992, shortly after the dissolution of the USSR. Since then, the two countries have maintained a strong partnership in various fields, including economic, cultural, and political. The relationship between Uzbekistan and South Korea is a testament to how two countries with different historical and geopolitical backgrounds can come together and build productive ties based on mutual interests. The growing diplomatic relationship has been complemented by regular high-level visits between the two countries, further strengthening the strategic partnership. Presidents, ministers, and lawmakers from both sides have met on several occasions to discuss key areas of cooperation.

South Korea, with its rapidly growing economy, recognized Uzbekistan as an important partner in Central Asia. Uzbekistan, on the other hand, sought to diversify its foreign relations and open up new avenues for economic cooperation following its independence.

Economic relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea have grown significantly over the years. South Korean companies have been actively involved in several key sectors in Uzbekistan, including construction, energy, infrastructure, textiles, and electronics. Both governments have sought to increase the volume of trade, and South Korea has become one of Uzbekistan's most important trading partners in East Asia. South Korea, being a global leader in IT and telecommunications can play an essential role in supporting Uzbekistan's ambitions to modernize its economy.

In addition to economic ties, cultural and educational

exchanges have played an important role in strengthening relations between the two countries. The Center for Korean Education in the capital serves as an important platform for promoting mutual understanding and fostering people-to-people ties.

South Korean language and culture (Korean wave: K-pop, Korean movies, Korean restaurants) have become increasingly popular in Uzbekistan, with many young Uzbeks learning Korean and seeking educational opportunities in South Korea. In turn, South Korean citizens and organizations are involved in cultural events, language education, and tourism exchanges.

In addition, the number of Uzbek students in South Korea has been steadily increasing. The Korean government has also offered scholarships for Uzbeks to pursue higher education in South Korea, resulting in a growing pool of professionals with strong ties to Korea.

Uzbek-Korean relations in the context of global challenges

What will Uzbek-Korean relations be like in the future? Will it be a quantitative expansion of cooperation or the construction of a new relationship in an era of global challenges?

We live in the era of the collapse of the old world order (the unipolar world). The old world order will no longer exist. We are moving towards a multipolar world. But this is not just an eclectic pluralism of many countries. It has its structure: the formation of regional centers of force. In turn, these centers are subject to the logic of polarization: Global

North and Global South, or Global West and Global East. Any productive analysis of foreign policy relations must proceed from this geopolitical configuration, which is growing in front of our eyes.

Of course, with the disintegration of the former world order, there is a temptation to raise the question of pan-Asian unity, although this is an elusive goal. But if we still talk about the axis of West Asia (Middle East and Transcaucasia), Central Asia, Southeast Asia, and Northeast Asia, what role can Korean-Uzbek relations play in it?

The relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea have the status of a special strategic partnership, while Uzbekistan has a comprehensive strategic partnership with Russia. At the same time, after Korea supports Russia's sanctions, Russia and South Korea are in unfriendly relations. Not only that, Russia has established strategic relations with North Korea. Russia and South Korea are Uzbekistan's largest economic partners. This is a complex and contradictory situation that needs to be resolved.

In Korean philosophy and life practice, there is a "win-win" principle. It means:

- creating a concept of co-development aimed at the cumulative effect of allied relations in the formation of a new world order;
- creation of targeted co-development programs;
- creation of joint analytical groups;
- joint political initiatives: Central Asia-East Asia axis (with an expansion of countries along this axis);
- mediatory role in the global confrontation.

Proposals on cooperation between UWED and the Republic of Korea

– Expansion of the internship system. It is important to expand the internships of UMED faculty and students in universities of the Republic of Korea and vice versa.

– Expansion of Korean themes in the topics of diploma, master's theses, and scientific dissertations defended at UMED.

– Expansion of joint seminars and conferences. Especially important are conferences on the formation of a new world order and the place of Korean-Uzbek relations in it. The main question: How to preserve the strategic partnership between our countries in the conditions of global confrontation, turbulence, and sanctions?

– Joint collections of articles. Topics: history and culture of CA, cooperation between Uzbekistan and ROK, monograph/textbook "History of Korea.". Promotion of publications of UMED scientists in Korean journals and vice versa (in Russian and Uzbek languages).

– Joint participation in projects of Korean and Uzbek granting organizations (Ministry of innovations).

– Joint participation in international projects.

– Establishment of the Center for Korean Studies at UMED based on parity funding.

– Translations of scientific and fiction literature.

– Scientific research projects.

– "Korean Diaspora of Uzbekistan: adaptive, socio-cultural and migration characteristics.

– Since 2000, sociological research has been conducted on the Korean Diaspora – 2000 (Academy of Korean Studies), 2001-2002, 2005-2006 (Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan), 2010 (Overseas Koreans Foundation), 2011 (field research as part of M. Tan’s dissertation), 2012 (Swiss Agency for Culture and Cooperation), “Izhtimoi fikr” surveys and other projects. More than 10 years have passed since the last project. It is important to find out what changes have occurred in the Korean diaspora over these years. The existence of previous studies provides a valuable and not always realized opportunity to trace changes in the object of study over a long period of time (20 years).

– “Korean diaspora of CIS natives in Korea”.

– Today the diaspora of Korean natives of the CIS (first of all, from Uzbekistan) in Korea is about 100 thousand people. This is a new phenomenon that needs to be studied by both Uzbekistan and Korea.

– “Uzbek Diaspora in Korea.”

– Uzbeks in Korea, whose numbers are expanding, are also a little-studied topic. They are being strengthened organizationally, formed as a community, are an important factor in supporting their families in Uzbekistan, and are one of the channels of penetration of Korean culture and business into Uzbekistan.

– Cultural programs to expand the acquaintance with Korea of UMED teachers and students and vice versa.

UZBEK-KOREAN RELATIONS: HISTORY, STATUS, PROSPECTS

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University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Korean Peninsula in the political sphere

Abstract. This study is dedicated to a comprehensive and critical analysis of the political relations between Uzbekistan and the Korean Peninsula countries, encompassing a period of over 30 years. It examines the historical evolution and genesis of Uzbekistan's political ties with the Korean Peninsula countries, with a primary focus on South Korea, the promotion of various initiatives by the leadership of South Korea towards Central Asian countries, and the establishment of various formats and mechanisms of bilateral interaction and their role in shaping the relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea. The article explores Uzbekistan's stance and approaches regarding the issues on the Korean Peninsula, along with an analysis of the factors influencing the cessation of diplomatic relations between Uzbekistan and North Korea.

Key words: Uzbekistan, Republic of Korea, North Korea, foreign policy, Koryo-saram, diplomatic relations, Central Asian initiatives, Korean Peninsula.

One of the goals of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to establish close ties with countries worldwide, particularly with developed states. In this context, as part of its foreign policy orientation towards the Asia-Pacific region (APR), alongside the development of comprehensive relations with Japan and China, the Republic of Uzbekistan (RU)

places significant importance on enhancing cooperation with the Republic of Korea (ROK). Transforming into an increasingly significant state in financial and economic terms within the APR, South Korea objectively seeks to further strengthen its political relations and economic positions in Uzbekistan and Central Asia as a whole.

Attention is particularly drawn to Uzbekistan's geostrategic significance - situated in the heart of Eurasia as a crucial communication route from the APR to Europe, with abundant mineral resources, a sufficiently skilled workforce, and a Korean diaspora of over 180,000 people residing in the country [Dunyo.info. 2024]. According to many South Korean experts, Uzbekistan stands as a key economic and political partner of Seoul not only in Central Asia but also across Eurasia, evident in the strategies put forth by the South Korean leadership.

As noted by a Korean expert, Uzbek-Korean relations began to develop even before Uzbekistan gained independence. Uzbekistan also expressed strong interest in improving relations with Korea. Uzbekistan displayed a keen desire to establish ties, making direct contact with Korean delegation leader Kim Jong-in at the first Korea-USSR government delegation meeting, held in Moscow in August 1990 right before Korea and the USSR established relations. Uzbek President Karimov, during an October 1990 meeting with Korea's deputy consulate general in Moscow, requested that Korea send an economic development investigation team to inspect his country's economic situation [Kwak Song Woong. 2022]. While Korea's interest in the Central Asian nations in the early 1990s was focused on the region's material resources and its desire to seek out new markets, the large number of

Koryo-saram (ethnic Koreans living in post-Soviet states) living in the region also played a major role. In the initial years, The Koryo-saram issue became a regular agenda item during meetings between Korean diplomats and Uzbek officials [Kwak. 2022].

For Uzbekistan, the Republic of Korea has always been an appealing direction in foreign policy. On one hand, the principle of multi-vectorism in foreign policy facilitates partner diversification for collaboration in seeking a balance between the influence of major actors. On the other hand, the pragmatic interests of Central Asian elites have always been more clearly expressed regarding states not directly within the orbit of direct geopolitical influence or pressure. In this regard, the experience of cooperation between Central Asian states and the Republic of Korea demonstrates a model of pragmatic mutually beneficial collaboration [Akmatalieva. 2021].

Despite the geographical distance between Korea and Uzbekistan, they are united by the emotional closeness of their people and shared goals in the pursuit of peace and prosperity. Historical exchanges between our countries have been established since the time of the Great Silk Road. A vivid confirmation of this is that Korean envoys are depicted in the frescoes at the "Afrosiab" Museum in Samarkand during an audience with the ruler of Samarkand in the late 7th century. Another important historical fact is that the star table described in the work of Mirzo Ulugbek, "Ziji Jadidi Kuragoniy," served as the basis for creating the ancient Korean calendar in the Choson state [Korea.net. 2022].

These facts have contributed to building a fairly effective model of partnership between the two countries. Strength-

ening political cooperation and mutual support on the international stage has become one of the priority areas of bilateral interaction. Moreover, based on pragmatism, South Korea puts forward a “core narrative” representing Korea as a significant partner for Central Asian countries with less “ideological baggage” than China, Russia, and the United States [The Oxus Society. 2022].

Over the years, the Republic of Korea has evolved into a time-tested strategic partner and a “close friend” in Asia [kun.uz. 2024]. Korean specialists, citing successful cooperation with Tashkent, advocate for intensifying collaboration with other countries in the region following the Uzbek pattern [Muratalieva. 2019].

From establishing diplomatic relations to strategic partnership

Uzbekistan plays a pivotal role in South Korea’s regional strategy. The foundation of the bilateral relationship between our nations was laid on December 30, 1991, when the Republic of Korea was among the first to recognize the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Over the course of more than thirty years, interactions between the two countries have progressed and strengthened, passing through several key stages.

These stages reflect deep historical ties and are characterized by a high level of dynamism in mutual exchanges. Regular high-level visits have given priority to Uzbek-South Korean relations for both sides. These meetings contribute to deepening mutual understanding and expanding cooperation in various fields, accompanied by the signing of impor-

tant agreements and memoranda of cooperation. Currently, the relations between the two countries are governed by over 197 intergovernmental agreements covering political, trade and economic, investment, scientific, and technical spheres, as well as education and culture.

In the consistent advancement and deepening of bilateral interactions, a crucial role is played by regular dialogue and intense mutual meetings between the leaders of the two countries. From 1992 to 2024 (as of June 2024), 20 summits have been held between the leaders of the two nations.

While the number of summits demonstrates the dynamics and degree of cooperation, the level of official visits by top officials underscores the areas of interest. Presidents of Uzbekistan have made more visits to Seoul than other Central Asian presidents, while among the countries in the region, Korean presidents have made more visits to Uzbekistan. These visits by top officials are not only characterized by their intensity but also are tied to specific events, such as the opening of joint ventures or cultural centers. These facts once again attest to the high level of relations and the priority accorded by both sides in their mutual dealings.

A new stage in the history of relations between Uzbekistan and Korea began after the proclamation of independence by the Central Asian countries in 1991. The significant Korean diaspora in Uzbekistan ultimately became one of the main factors contributing to the establishment of close partnerships between the two countries in recent years. Currently, the Korean community in the Republic of Uzbekistan numbers around 180,000 people, making it the largest diaspora in the CIS countries. For the Republic of Korea, this partnership is also driven by Uzbekistan's rich resource, scientific

and technical, and human potential, while for our country, it is primarily motivated by the opportunity to receive financial, investment, and scientific and technical support from Korea, as well as to leverage Korea's extensive experience in modernizing its economy in the reform efforts of Uzbekistan.

At the initial stage, a strong impetus to the activation of relations between the two countries was given by the visit of President of the Republic of Korea Kim Young-sam to the Republic of Uzbekistan in June 1994 and the reciprocal visit of President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov to Korea in February 1995. Despite being in their nascent stages, the outcomes of these visits were groundbreaking, as South Korea agreed to invest in Uzbekistan's heavy industry and transfer technology, thereby laying the foundation for an entire automotive industry in Central Asia. In 1996, the South Korean company "Daewoo" opened its first plant in Uzbekistan, and the country became a member of the select group of global automotive powers as a manufacturer of its cars.

According to European experts, investments from South Korea in the industrial and energy sectors are unique for the country, whereas other external players (Russia, China, the EU, and the USA) were primarily interested in exploiting the natural resources of Central Asia [Popławski. 2024].

One important political aspect to emphasize is that most post-Soviet republics initially viewed South Korea with caution due to its close relations with the USA. However, Uzbekistan sought an active political dialogue with Seoul as a modern symbol of Asian dynamism and technological advancement [Rakhimov, Sung. 2016]. Even during the period of Western sanctions on Uzbekistan following the Andijan

events, they had no impact on the development of mutual relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea. A significant factor in this was the presence of close friendly ties between leaders and political circles, Korea's economic and investment presence in Uzbekistan, and most importantly, the large Korean diaspora in Uzbekistan.

In the 2000s, South Korea, following the Asian crisis, embarked on a quest to navigate and establish new political and economic partnerships. In contrast to the initial years of collaboration, which were rooted in the interrelations of the political elites of both nations, the new leadership of Seoul under President Roh Moo-hyun (2003–2008) opted to institutionalize the mutual cooperation with Central Asian countries. Consequently, South Korea's leader in 2004 launched the ***Comprehensive Central Asia Initiative***, marking Korea's first strategic move targeting the region.

This strategy aimed to bolster diplomatic ties, foster various economic sectors, including enhancing business and ensuring energy security. The introduction of this strategy injected dynamism into South Korea's relations with Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan, leading to a rapid expansion of their cooperative endeavors.

Uzbekistan and South Korea engaged in continuous inter-governmental dialogue, characterized by regular high-level meetings. As a result, Uzbekistan was among the first partners to sign a Joint Declaration on Strategic Partnership with the Republic of Korea in 2006.

During his presidency (2008-2013), Lee Myung-bak incorporated Central Asia into his broader New Asia Initiative launched in 2009, prioritizing Korea's relations with its Asian neighbors and signaling an expansion of the country's

focus beyond its traditional relationships with the US, China, Russia, and Japan [The Oxus Society. 2022]. This initiative aimed to integrate the extensive logistical and transport infrastructure of Central Asian countries with Korea.

Building on the policies of his predecessor, President Park Geun-hye (2013-2017) introduced her “**New Northern Policy,**” also known as the **Eurasian Initiative**. This initiative, unveiled a month after China proposed the “Belt and Road Initiative” in 2013, emphasized “one continent, creative continent, and peaceful continent,” concentrating on developing transportation, energy, and trade networks across the Eurasian continent.

Park Geun-hye’s Eurasian initiative gained further momentum under the leadership of Moon Jae-in (2017-2023). The initiative sought to invigorate South Korea’s engagement with Eurasian continental states in its foreign policy. The New Northern Policy (NNP), like the New Southern Policy, formed part of South Korea’s external policy platform aimed at creating a “New Economic Map of the Korean Peninsula [Akmatalieva. 2021].”

Personal relationships between the leaders of both countries and their approaches to diplomacy play a pivotal role in their political relations. During his tenure as Mayor of Seoul, Lee Myung-bak bestowed the title of honorary citizen of Seoul upon the first President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, for his significant contribution to fostering friendship between the two nations [The Korea Times. 2010]. In May 2015, Karimov chose Seoul as the destination for his first foreign visit after re-election, underscoring Uzbekistan’s prioritization of South Korea in its foreign policy in a new era.

Mutual expectations and interests in cooperation have

consistently been expressed during official visits by top officials. These expectations have been continuously adjusted in line with global trends in world politics, regional changes, and shifts in the domestic policies of states. The intensification of Eurasian initiatives by China with the “Belt and Road Initiative,” Russia’s vision for Greater Eurasia, the US’s New Silk Road, Japan’s Silk Road Diplomacy, and others prompted Seoul to put forth its strategic visions—the “Eurasian Initiative” and the “New Northern Policy” [Akmatalieva. 2021]. Tashkent’s stance, grounded in balancing its external partners, held significant importance for South Korea’s strategic and systematic approaches to the region.

The professor from Chonnam National University acknowledges that the New Northern Policy should be viewed not only as a shift in South Korea’s diplomatic policy but also as a strategy towards “open regionalism [The Korea Times, 2021].”

According to the *representative from the Ministry of Unification, Lee Yu Jin*, the NNP of South Korea aims at connecting the Korean Peninsula, the Russian Far East, and Eurasia. It will also provide a foundation for the institutionalization of South Korea’s international cooperation, create new points of economic growth, expand humanitarian ties, and aim at establishing an integration network. While Russia was given a central role in this strategy, special emphasis was also placed on Central Asia, where Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan have the potential to act as conduits in implementing this strategy [Muratalieva. 2019].

During a visit to South Korea, President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, supporting this initiative, proposed aligning South Korea’s “New Northern Policy” with China’s “Belt

and Road” initiative and the EU’s new strategy to enhance Europe-Asia connectivity. This alignment, according to the Uzbek side, will help in creating transportation and logistics routes linking Central Asia through Russia, China, and Korea to the markets of Europe, Northeast Asia, Southeast Asia, and allowing the countries of the region access to seaports [Muratalieva. 2019].

Despite South Korea advancing its strategies during each presidency, frequent changes in leadership in Seoul have hindered the continuous implementation of declared strategies, including with Uzbekistan. In this regard, experts believe that despite the existence of individual strategies, South Korea’s policy in Central Asia lacks conceptual clarity [Muratalieva. 2019].

The relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea, initially focused on strengthening political and economic cooperation in the early years, expanded to include other areas after a change in government in Uzbekistan. Additionally, the escalating competition and trade wars between the USA and China began to impact Korean-Chinese bilateral relations, evident in the reduction of Chinese rare earth resources to Korea. In response, the Korean side began exploring alternative options, including the vast mineral reserves of Uzbekistan.

This factor led to a significant rapprochement between South Korea and Uzbekistan, as well as with the countries of Central Asia in general. This is evident in the increased frequency of visits, meetings, and negotiations between the two leaders, as well as the increased activity of Korean businesses in the development of mineral resources and energy sectors. Against this backdrop, Uzbekistan and Korea signed a

Declaration in 2019, elevating the relations between the two countries to a special strategic partnership level. Furthermore, the Uzbek side expressed its intention to elevate the relationship between Uzbekistan and South Korea to an alliance level, as stated by President Sh. Mirziyoyev during the visit of South Korean President Moon Jae-in to Uzbekistan in December 2021. Remarkably, Uzbekistan is the only country in Central Asia and the fourth country globally with which Seoul has established a “*special strategic partnership*.”

During this period, contacts intensified on various platforms, notably in the “South Korea + Central Asia” format. It was announced that the “South Korea-Central Asia” format would be elevated to the level of heads of state. Additionally, it was announced that the first summit of the presidents would be held in Seoul in 2025 [Popławski. 2024]. According to expert, this will bolster the positions of Central Asian countries in relation to Russia and China, although these relationships currently lack the potential to balance the influence of these two leading powers [Popławski. 2024].

Tashkent and Seoul continue to build a mutually beneficial partnership, prioritizing the strengthening of political dialogue as a crucial condition for expanding interstate cooperation, including during the new leadership era in Korea under President Yun Sok Yol. On September 19, 2023, the President of Uzbekistan met with the President of South Korea on the sidelines of the UN General Assembly session in New York, and on November 21, 2023, a phone call between the two leaders took place. President of South Korea Yun Sok Yol paid a state visit to Uzbekistan in June 2024.

As noted by *European expert M. Poplavsky*, at the beginning of 2024, the “**K-Silk Road**” collaboration was announced,

representing another, yet more comprehensive strategy by South Korea for the Central Asian region. During the visit of South Korean President Yun Sok Yul to Uzbekistan, the parties discussed bilateral issues outlined in this Korean strategy. Of particular importance is the emphasis placed during the leaders' meeting on fostering close contacts in the realms of security and defense, specifically in combating cybercrime, terrorism, and extremism.

In the official meeting, the Korean president stated that “the Republic of Korea supports Uzbekistan’s efforts in implementing reforms and, as a special strategic partner, will continue to closely collaborate in Uzbekistan’s social, economic, and democratic development [IntelliNews. 2024].”

President Yun Sok Yul’s visit to Uzbekistan once again demonstrates Seoul’s sincere interest in advancing relations with Tashkent. Currently, Uzbekistan is becoming a desired partner for South Korea in terms of securing supply chains and obtaining resources crucial for its energy-intensive and advanced economy. Given that South Korea ranks eighth globally in energy consumption and plays a significant role in the automotive industry, including the production of batteries for electric vehicles and semiconductors for developing new technological ventures, the South Korean government aims to reduce its dependence on imports from China, including lithium imports (as China controls around 70% of this market) [Popławski. 2024].

Another important aspect of cooperation is labor migration, as the demographic decline in South Korea has made its labor market relatively open to workers from Central Asia, particularly from Uzbekistan. Close collaboration in this sphere contributes to stabilizing Korea’s labor market, shap-

ing its workforce, and ultimately ensuring the stable development of the Republic of Korea's economy. Under this policy in 2024, 37,200 Uzbek citizens (out of a total of 165,000 workers) were admitted through an organized labor migration system and granted work permits in South Korea.

Overall, these initiatives form part of South Korea's new strategy towards the Central Asian region, which President Yun Sok Yul advocated during his visit and which was endorsed by the President of Uzbekistan. This strategy is designed to align with the interests not only of Seoul but also of the Central Asian countries. It is built upon four main pillars: raw materials and minerals; development assistance; cultural and humanitarian exchange; and government-business cooperation. These are the focal points being emphasized in Uzbekistan, fully aligning with the interests of our state.

However, many experts point out that while Seoul is indeed a long-term and trustworthy partner for Tashkent, in recent years, due to the Ukrainian crisis, there has been significant competition for Central Asia among global powers such as Russia, Western countries, and notably China. Today, Beijing significantly outpaces both Russia and South Korea in terms of trade and investment metrics. Given this, it will be challenging for South Korea to penetrate the market and carve out its niche.

Interparliamentary relations constitute a crucial element of Uzbek-South Korean ties. During the visit of the South Korean parliament delegation in late August 1995 and the official visit in May 1996 of a delegation from the Oliy Majlis led by E. Khalilov, connections between the parliaments of the two countries were established and further developed. Parliamentarians from both nations regularly hold meet-

ings and exchanges, fostering the development of the legislative framework for bilateral cooperation and strengthening friendly ties between the peoples. Friendship parliamentary groups play a pivotal role in this process, exchanging experiences and best practices. Notably, visits to Uzbekistan by the speakers of the National Assembly of the Republic of Korea, Chung Sye Gyun (2017), and Park Byeong Seok (2021), have taken place. Friendship groups have been established in the parliaments of both countries. Their joint sessions were held online in June 2021 and in Tashkent in August 2022.

In turn, the parties are *actively engaged in diplomatic relations*. Since 1995, the foreign ministries of the two countries have been conducting regular political consultations, consistently reaffirming their shared positions on many aspects of foreign policy. Sixteen rounds of ***inter-ministerial political consultations*** have been held (the latest on March 25, 2024, in Tashkent). On September 11, 2023, the ***1st Strategic Dialogue*** at the level of foreign ministers took place during the official visit of the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan, B. Saidov, to Korea. Additionally, a joint mechanism for political consultations with five Central Asian countries has been in place since November 2007, namely the annual “Republic of Korea + Central Asia” Forum, whose secretariat was established in 2017 (the 16th session was held in Ashgabat on November 1, 2023).

Furthermore, experts emphasize that South Korea’s interactions with regional countries occur at the bilateral level, while the multilateral mechanism “5+1” (ROK + CA) remains highly ineffective. At least Korean experts lament this, noting the critically low level of representation from the Central Asian republics at these meetings [Muratalieva. 2019].

South Korea enjoys a distinctly positive image in Central Asia and, alongside Russia, China, the USA, Japan, and the EU, ranks among Uzbekistan's largest investors [Rakhimov, Sung. 2016]. From the regional perspective, South Korea does not hinder cooperation with a contentious political agenda and does not pose a security threat. South Korea's "soft power," including its pop culture, which is popular in the region, is a significant factor in building people-to-people diplomacy [Popławski. 2024].

As noted by *Kyrgyz expert N. Murataliev*, the strengths of cooperation with South Korea include Seoul's relative flexibility and contractual reliability, as it lacks significant geopolitical interests in Central Asia. In this respect, Korean companies stand out favorably from other players such as China and Russia. Nevertheless, there are some problematic aspects in the ROK's collaboration with Uzbekistan.

Firstly, as evidenced by an analysis of trade relations, collaboration between the ROK and RUz largely remains resource-oriented. The exported goods predominantly consist of raw materials without diversification into new product lines.

Secondly, the negative effects of cooperation stemming from failed projects persist. Past unsuccessful instances of collaboration with regional countries (*such as the case of Korean investment in the Ustyurt gas chemical complex*) negatively impact both the flow of Korean investments and the development and implementation of new projects.

Thirdly, the multilateral format is effectively non-functional. Despite two "CA + South Korea" forums being held post-pandemic, tangible outcomes in the form of multilateral projects have not materialized. The Forum discussions have

been limited to topics of mutual cooperation that remain on paper without practical application.

V. Norov, Director of ISMI, emphasized that Uzbekistan highly values the efforts of the Republic of Korea government as the primary inspiration and coordinator of the Forum. However, additional efforts from all sides are required to transform it into a significant platform for strengthening multi-dimensional cooperation and an effective mechanism for the practical implementation of priority projects that serve the interests of all participants [isrs.uz. 2018].

Lastly, a separate issue worth highlighting is the regulation of migration from Uzbekistan to South Korea. Although there is a labor agreement between our states, there are mutually resolvable issues regarding improving the situation in this area. Specifically, Kazakhstan's case with visa-free travel encountered some problems. Consequently, Seoul is cautious about repeating a similar history and both sides are meticulously addressing this matter. Nevertheless, delaying the resolution of this issue hampers substantial progress in the development of tourism between the countries, despite Uzbekistan including South Korea in the list of countries with visa-free access to its territory.

For reference: *Following the introduction of a visa-free regime in February 2018, valid for 30 days for citizens of the Republic of Korea, the total number of visitors from South Korea to Uzbekistan in 2019 reached approximately 36,000 individuals, marking a 30.3% increase. In 2023, the number of Korean tourists increased by 37,100, and during January-August 2024, 28,200 Koreans visited Uzbekistan.*

Currently, Uzbek-Korean relations require a new impetus for advancing into a new phase of bilateral cooperation char-

acterized by even closer friendship. Key attributes such as mutual understanding, mutual respect, cultural similarities, shared perspectives on regional security issues, and close mutually beneficial trade and economic cooperation should form the foundation of our relations.

In summary, the mutually beneficial Uzbek-South Korean relations have come a long way since their establishment in 1992, serving as an exemplar of a unique strategic partnership. The fact that all recent South Korean presidents have visited Uzbekistan over the past decade (in 2010, 2012, 2014, 2019, and 2024) demonstrates Seoul's sincere interest in the country.

South Korean experts believe that South Korea and the Central Asian republics should always remember the history of mutual exchange and cooperation achieved by past generations, utilizing it as a foundation upon which they can move towards a new era [Kwak. 2022].

Compared to other players, South Korea has limited influence in Central Asia. However, Seoul's lack of geopolitical ambitions contributes to its participation not arousing the same suspicions or negative reactions as those from major players like Russia, China, or Western countries. Furthermore, South Korea's successful experience in industrialization and modernization could potentially serve as a development model for Central Asia. Korea's presence assists Uzbekistan in diversifying its foreign policy and external economic ties, export routes, and sources of investments.

Relations between Uzbekistan and the DPRK

It is important to emphasize that Uzbekistan's relations with the two Korean states in the early stages of indepen-

dence were primarily pragmatic and devoid of politicization. The Democratic People's Republic of Korea was among the first to recognize the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 26, 1991. Subsequently, on February 7, 1992, diplomatic relations were established between our countries, leading to the opening of the North Korean Embassy in Tashkent. The significance of this direction in Pyongyang's foreign policy is evidenced by the fact that North Korean embassies in the CIS states operated only in Russia and Uzbekistan [eurasia.upf. 2013]. Furthermore, the presence of a Korean diaspora in the country played a pivotal role in establishing diplomatic relations.

In earlier sections, the history of the Korean diaspora's resettlement in Uzbekistan in the 1930s was outlined. Additionally, certain historical facts should be mentioned. Uzbekistan has been home to many Koreans, including participants of the Korean War from 1950 to 1953. Following Korea's liberation from Japanese colonial rule in 1945 and its division into what would become the DPRK and the Republic of Korea, the Soviet Union not only provided military-technical and economic assistance to the DPRK but also sent its specialists, among whom were many Korean-Uzbekistanis [eurasia.upf. 2013].

By the late 1950s and early 1960s, many of them returned to Uzbekistan and subsequently became prominent party and state figures, business leaders. The older generation of most Koreans residing in Uzbekistan are descendants from the northern part of the Korean Peninsula, prompting Pyongyang to actively support the Korean Diaspora in Uzbekistan.

Over the years following the establishment of diplomatic

relations, Uzbekistan and the DPRK have traversed a challenging path of cooperation, managing to maintain their relationship despite various difficulties and economic crises faced by both countries post the USSR's dissolution. In the initial stages of interaction, the parties closely collaborated in the cultural and humanitarian spheres. Particularly, North Korean artists and cultural figures served as the initial bridge to their ancestral homeland. Not only artists but also Korean language teachers, traditional medicine practitioners, and others actively contributed to strengthening bilateral ties between Uzbekistan and the DPRK. A significant link connecting Tashkent and Pyongyang was the Uzbekistan-DPRK Friendship Forum, operational since 2009.

As part of its foreign policy approach towards the Asia-Pacific region, including South and North Korea, Uzbekistan places importance on maintaining peace and stability on the Korean Peninsula, thereby supporting its non-nuclear status. In 2001, Uzbekistan supported the DPRK's accession to the Asian Development Bank. Delegations Ministry of foreign affairs from both countries exchanged visits in 2000-2002. Within the framework of the 3rd Committee of the UN General Assembly in 2005, both sides supported each other's positions on a parity basis, advocating for the comprehensive strengthening of the UN's role in addressing regional and international issues [eurasia.upf. 2013].

In the 1990s, the two countries had modest trade and economic relations. Several joint ventures involving North Korean capital operated in Uzbekistan, focusing on producing food products and consumer goods. For instance, the Uzbek-North Korean joint venture "Taedongang" in the food industry was engaged in livestock and fishing produc-

tion. Other North Korean companies in Uzbekistan were mainly involved in agriculture, medicine, trade, as well as in the service and tourism sectors. Uzbekistan's exports to the DPRK primarily comprised services, while the import list included chemical fibers, non-precious metal products, mechanical equipment, agricultural fertilizers, and consumer goods. However, starting from the 2000s, these trade relations began to significantly decline, influenced not only by international circumstances but also by the lack of transportation and logistical connections between the two states.

Nevertheless, the escalation of international circumstances surrounding North Korea due to its nuclear capabilities and the deteriorating relations between North and South Korea directly impacted bilateral relations between the DPRK and Uzbekistan, affecting economic and cultural-humanitarian exchanges. As a result of these events, political contacts between the two countries were limited to exchanging messages on commemorative dates and holding protocol events. Visa issues from the North Korean side also became more stringent for Uzbekistan.

As a result, by mutual agreement and considering the practical absence of mutual economic interest, North Korea decided to close its embassy in Uzbekistan in July 2016 as part of restructuring its missions in the CIS. All North Korean diplomats left the country, and the property, the embassy building itself, and other assets were liquidated [Sohu. 2016].

In brief analysis of the reasons for the termination of diplomatic relations, it should be noted that after Pyongyang conducted nuclear tests in January 2016, Seoul not only

severed all cooperation with the DPRK but also actively engaged in negotiations with other countries, seeking to persuade them to cease cooperation with North Korea. With “strong recommendations” to discontinue cooperation with the DPRK, South Korean diplomats had already visited many countries in Asia and Africa that maintain friendly contacts with Pyongyang [Кирьянов. 2016]. South Korea’s stance, particularly under President Park Geun-hye, intensified towards isolating North Korea, depriving it of all currency-earning channels and dealing a blow to the North’s economy to compel it to give up its nuclear weapons.

***For reference,** international sanctions against North Korea due to Pyongyang’s nuclear program were imposed after its first nuclear test in 2006.*

The Chinese publication “Sohu” points to the closure of the North Korean diplomatic mission in Tashkent as a result of Uzbekistan’s condemnation of North Korea’s nuclear tests, in which the South Korean government also played a certain role. Supporting this notion, the Russian newspaper “Rossiyskaya Gazeta,” citing South Korean media reports, stated that official Seoul’s pressure on Uzbekistan led to the DPRK mission being forced to leave the country [Кирьянов. 2016].

Additionally, as Russian experts note, in May 2016, the Prime Minister of South Korea, Hwang Kyo-ahn, visited Uzbekistan. Numerous cooperation agreements were signed during that visit. Furthermore, South Korea is one of the largest foreign investors in Uzbekistan and has managed to establish a strong presence there. Experts speculate that the visit involved a form of exchange akin to “investment and trade cooperation in exchange for your withdrawal or at

least a reduction in ties with the North [Кириянов. 2016].”

However, it should be emphasized that this version does not align with Uzbekistan’s political stance, which pursues an independent foreign policy course that categorically excludes external “recommendations” that could influence the country’s policy. Moreover, officials in Tashkent stated that the relations between the RUz and DPRK did not significantly deteriorate and that the closure of the embassy does not signify a diplomatic rift [Sohu. 2016].

Some media outlets linked the lively discussion surrounding the closure of the North Korean mission in Uzbekistan to the fact that following the closure of the North Korean embassy in Kazakhstan in 1998, the embassy in Tashkent remained the only North Korean diplomatic mission in Central Asia.

The Chinese publication Sohu, citing analysts, believes that North Korea closed its embassy in Uzbekistan to prevent the defection of diplomats [Sohu. 2016]. During this period, there was a rise in defections by North Korean diplomats to other countries, particularly the defection of diplomats to South Korea, which greatly concerned the North Korean government.

Nevertheless, some experts believe that a complex of factors likely played a role. It is evident that North Korea had long-standing financial difficulties in supporting its missions’ operations, so it is possible that on one hand, North Korea faced financial issues, and on the other, the Uzbekistan government hinted that “it was time to leave”. Hence, they decided to close everything down, transferring responsibilities to the North Korean embassy in Moscow [Кириянов. 2016].

Uzbekistan's position on the situation on the Korean Peninsula

Since the early years of independence, Uzbekistan has chosen a path of peaceful and constructive development based on humanistic values and peaceful coexistence. In this context, Uzbekistan strongly supports South Korea's policy on resolving North Korean issues and ensuring peace and security on the Korean Peninsula. As the initiator of the creation of the "Central Asia - Nuclear-Weapon-Free Zone" (CANWFZ) in 1993 [INFCIRC/864. 2014], Uzbekistan advocates for the swift commencement of the denuclearization process on the Korean Peninsula and calls on the North Korean side to refrain from testing all forms of weapons of mass destruction, which will undoubtedly contribute to furthering inter-Korean relations and promoting integration in the region [Юн Со Чжон, О Хен У, Korea.net. 2021].

An analysis of statements from Uzbekistan's foreign policy department on this matter reveals that Tashkent consistently advocates, including within the framework of the UN, for the resolution of the situation on the Korean Peninsula. It is particularly noteworthy that in the realm of multilateral cooperation, Uzbekistan welcomes the resumption of inter-Korean dialogue and agreements to hold new summits between South Korea and North Korea, while reaffirming its unwavering support for South Korea's efforts to establish peace, stability, and security on the Korean Peninsula.

The Uzbek Ministry of Foreign Affairs, expressing concern over North Korea's launch of a carrier rocket in 2010, stated that "Uzbekistan calls on Pyongyang to refrain from taking unilateral actions aimed at further escalating tensions and to resolve existing contradictions through peaceful diplomatic means [UzDaily.uz. 2010]."

In addressing the situation on the Korean Peninsula, Tashkent places significant importance on Seoul's "New Northern Policy" initiative. South Korea's proposal, involving the restoration of railway and road connections, undoubtedly opens new perspectives for expanding cooperation on the Korean Peninsula with countries across the vast Eurasian region, including Central Asia, transforming it into a continent with a unified transport and logistics system and robust trade and economic ties [isrs.uz. 2018].

The support extended by Tashkent for Seoul's stance on Korean Peninsula issues is highly appreciated by official circles in South Korea. *Nam Gwan-pyo*, Deputy Director of the Office of National Security at the South Korean President's administration, highlighted that Uzbekistan not only occupies a central position in Central Asia but is also a strategically important point in geopolitical and geoeconomic terms. According to the specialist, Uzbekistan, as the initiator of the denuclearization movement in Central Asia, harbors a strong desire for a world free of nuclear weapons. The country actively supports Seoul in addressing Pyongyang's nuclear issue [Kim. The Korea Times. 2017]. Overall, Tashkent welcomes Seoul's peace-oriented policy aimed at establishing peace on the Korean Peninsula, a stance that holds significant importance for global security.

Positions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea on important points of the international agenda

The collaboration between the two countries in the field of foreign policy is characterized by an increasing degree of mutual support when addressing security issues in the Asian

continent. Recently, there has been an expansion of the scope of interaction between the two nations on the international stage, exerting a positive influence on the development of security in Asia as a whole and in its specific regions. For instance, South Korea backs Uzbekistan's initiative to establish a nuclear-weapon-free zone in Central Asia.

Moreover, Uzbekistan highly values the relationships between the Republic of Korea and other countries in the Asia-Pacific region, recognizing primarily Seoul's heightened role in ensuring stability on the Korean Peninsula and its efforts in resolving the issue of reunification between the two Koreas. A significant catalyst in this regard is also South Korea's interest in reviving the Great Silk Road and forming an economic union of Muslim countries (Turkey, Iran, Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Central Asian nations). Such an alliance, with access to the Indian and Pacific Oceans, could potentially serve as an effective counterbalance to international groupings of economically developed countries in the long term.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has successfully fostered a close dialogue with the Republic of Korea on a wide range of international and regional issues. Political consultations held regularly address serious matters related to the establishment of a multipolar world order, the new architecture of Asian security, the roles and positions of the UN, OSCE, NATO, and other institutions in maintaining stability and security in Asia. Legal support from the South Korean side, alongside Japan and the EU, to Central Asian countries in drafting a Treaty on creating a nuclear-weapon-free zone in the region has also enabled the accumulation of experience in bilateral practical cooperation when addressing significant regional security issues.

Experts believe that the countries share close and similar positions on current regional and international security problems. Both South Korea and Uzbekistan adhere to principles of openness, multilateralism, and developing their regions as spaces for mutually beneficial cooperation.

The development of political relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea is dynamic, both at the bilateral level and within the framework of the UN and its specialized agencies. Such cooperation enables the countries to coordinate efforts in addressing global and regional issues, strengthen their positions on the international stage, and jointly promote initiatives aimed at ensuring stability and sustainable development.

Furthermore, successful collaboration between the two countries within international organizations and the coordination of Seoul and Tashkent's actions on the international stage have been ongoing. In recent years, Uzbekistan has repeatedly supported South Korea, including during elections for non-permanent members of the UN Security Council, in the Inter-Parliamentary Union, at the International Organization for Standardization, and during the UN General Assembly session on banning radioactive waste in North Korea. Emphasizing the importance of stability on the Korean Peninsula, Tashkent welcomed the summit between the leaders of North Korea and South Korea in Pyongyang in June 2000. The Uzbek side expressed hope that the meeting of the leaders of the two Korean states would contribute to peace and security in East Asia and globally, as well as to the development of cooperation between the North and the South.

Specialists and officials in South Korea have notably expressed their support for the candidacy of Pan Gi Mun for

the position of Secretary-General of the United Nations, endorsed by the first President of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov [The Korea Times. 2010].

In recent years alone, Uzbekistan has backed South Korea's candidacy in various UN bodies such as UNCITRAL (2018), ECOSOC (2016, 2019, and 2022), UNHRC (2015, 2019, and 2022), the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (2017 and 2021), the International Law Commission (2016), the Human Rights Committee (2019-2022), the Committee on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (2019-2022), the Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2019-2022), and as a non-permanent member of the UN Security Council (2024-2025).

Conversely, South Korea also supports Uzbekistan's foreign policy initiatives aimed at ensuring regional security, particularly addressing issues such as non-proliferation of weapons of mass destruction worldwide.

Within the realm of international cooperation, Seoul has endorsed and co-authored resolutions initiated by Uzbekistan in the UN General Assembly: focusing on "Strengthening regional and international cooperation to ensure peace, stability and sustainable development in the Central Asian region"; "Enlightenment and religious tolerance" (2018), "Sustainable tourism and sustainable development in Central Asia" (2019), "Enhancing the role of parliaments in accelerating the achievement of the SDGs" (2022), and declaring "2027 the International Year of Sustainable and Resilient Tourism" (2024).

Additionally, South Korea has supported Uzbekistan's candidacies in the UN Human Rights Council for 2021-2023, as well as Samarkand's bid to host the 25th session

of the UN World Tourism Organization General Assembly in 2023, among numerous other instances [The Korea Herald. 2024].

Notably, the most active collaboration with Korea among international economic organizations occurs within the framework of Uzbekistan's accession process to the World Trade Organization (WTO). South Korea's Permanent Representatives in Geneva since 2002 have led the Working group on Uzbekistan's WTO accession. Specifically, during the first state visit of Uzbekistan's President Sh. Mirziyoyev to South Korea in 2017, agreements were reached for technical, consultative, and expert support from Korean specialists regarding Uzbekistan's WTO accession, further affirming Seoul's comprehensive readiness to assist Uzbekistan.

As noted by *the Deputy Director of the Institute for Strategic and Regional Studies A. Nematov*, the mutual commitment to enhancing bilateral relations has matured into a robust, systematic, and mutually beneficial partnership. This level of collaboration is evident in the mutual support within international organizations, the alignment of Uzbekistan and South Korea's positions on pressing regional and international security issues. In this context, South Korea provides invaluable technical, consultative, and expert support to Uzbekistan throughout its WTO accession process, aiding in assessing the implications of joining the organization and conducting a review of national legislation in accordance with agreement requirements [Alimova. 2022].

Uzbekistan has successfully fostered a close dialogue with the Republic of Korea on a wide range of international and regional issues. Both sides have emphasized the necessity of a multipolar world order, a new architecture for

Asian security, and the leading role of international organizations in maintaining stability at global and regional levels. Both countries are keen on intensifying joint efforts to promote the Afghan recovery process. Seoul shares Tashkent's stance on the swift stabilization of the situation in Afghanistan.

During the official visit of South Korean President No Mu Hyun to Uzbekistan in 2005, a Joint Declaration was signed, reflecting Tashkent's support for Seoul's official foreign policy course towards achieving peace and stability in North-east Asia, South Korea's efforts towards the unification of the two Koreas, and the peaceful resolution of the North Korean nuclear issue.

Furthermore, there is alignment or proximity in the positions of both countries regarding countering international terrorism and extremism, arms and drug trafficking, and the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction. In this context, the Korean side expresses readiness to continue collaborating with Uzbekistan at both bilateral and multi-lateral levels.

In recent years, the close interaction between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea has taken on a systemic nature. During negotiations, the leaders of both countries consistently affirm their alignment on regional and international issues. Specifically, our head of state endorsed the proposal to hold the first "Central Asia - Republic of Korea" summit in Seoul in 2025 and expressed support for President Yun Sok Yol's firm actions to ensure peace and stability on the Korean Peninsula.

Overall, an analysis of the current trends in Uzbek-South Korean relations suggests that there is potential for a growth

in their dynamics in the medium term. It appears that in the long run, the most advantageous form of cooperation between the two countries will be investment and scientific-technical collaboration. However, in the near future, trade relations are likely to remain the primary form of interaction. Future directions of the partnership could also include emerging areas of cooperation such as green economy, digitalization, and innovation.

Considering the ample untapped opportunities in developing various trade and economic cooperation avenues between Uzbekistan and South Korea, it is crucial to attract major South Korean corporations as well as small and medium-sized private enterprises from both countries to engage in collaboration. Emphasizing the importance of devising new mechanisms for bilateral investment and scientific-technical cooperation with more active involvement of U.S., Japanese, and EU investments in joint projects, the partnership between the two nations can ascend to a new qualitative level.

A vital factor in elevating relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea to a qualitatively new level of partnership is seen in the comprehensive development of bilateral political dialogue. This will foster the process of economic integration and ensure stability in Central Asia. In this context, the development and launch of South Korea's new strategy specifically tailored for Central Asia, the "K-Silk Road," is aimed at providing a fresh impetus for the comprehensive deepening of cooperation between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea. It aims to leverage significant untapped opportunities for further development in their collaboration.

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COOPERATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND KOREA IN THE ECONOMIC SPHERE

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Introduction

The establishment of diplomatic relations in 1992 marked the beginning of formal economic ties. Initial cooperation focused on trade and investment, with South Korean companies exploring opportunities in Uzbekistan's energy, agriculture, and infrastructure sectors. The early years laid the foundation for a more comprehensive partnership that would develop in subsequent decades.

In 2022, countries celebrated the 30th anniversary of diplomatic relations between South Korea and the Central Asian countries. Over the years, the partnership between the Republic of Korea and Uzbekistan has significantly expanded within both bilateral and multilaterally. Although, strategic partnership between countries is expanding, geographical location and absence of the direct land transport links between them remains as the major bottleneck for further facilitation of cooperation. There are potential and possibilities for extending cooperation between Central Asia and South Korea, especially Uzbekistan. Promising areas of cooperation include joint technology projects for the implementation of e-government, digital economy, innovative potential in energy, industry, infrastructure, logistics centers, textile and food industry, mechanical and electri-

cal engineering, agriculture, and the development of transit corridors between Asia and Europe through the region (Rakhimov M., 2022).

Uzbek-Korean relations are flourishing across various sectors including trade, economics, politics, culture, humanitarian efforts, transportation, and communication. The extensive legal framework for bilateral cooperation comprises over 200 documents governing collaboration in diverse areas. Notably, the Joint Declaration on Strategic Partnership between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea (2006) and the Joint Statement on the Comprehensive Deepening of Strategic Partnership Relations (2017) stand as pivotal documents in this regard (Zhonibekov Z., Avvalboev I., 2024).

I. Bilateral trade relations

It is worth noting that, economic reforms implemented in the Republic have led to rapid growth in trade relations with foreign countries. The decisions made to boost export potential will enable local companies to gain more experience in working in foreign markets, ultimately giving them a competitive advantage in global trade. As a result of the measures taken in the Republic in recent years to stimulate exports, optimize imports, and ensure balanced foreign trade, the foreign trade turnover in the country reached 62.6 billion US dollars in December 2023. This marked a 23.9% increase compared to the same period in 2022, amounting to a rise of 12.1 billion US dollars. (Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024).

<p>PRC</p> <p>FTT – 13 722,0</p> <p>Export : 2 461,8 Import : 11 260,1</p> <p> 3,7 %</p>				
<p>Turkmenistan</p> <p>FTT – 1 094,4</p> <p>Export : 171,2 Import : 923,2</p> <p> 1,4 %</p>				

Figure 1. Countries with the highest share of foreign trade with the Republic of Uzbekistan. – https://stat.uz/img/press_reliz_tashi_savdo_eng_yanvar_dekabr_20_12-engokok.pdf

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan carries out trade relations with 198 countries of the world. The largest volume of foreign trade turnover was recorded with China (21.9%), Russia (15.8%), Kazakhstan (7.0%), Türkiye (5.0%) and the Republic of Korea (3.7%) (see figure 1).

Trade cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea has been developing rapidly in recent years. Bilateral trade volume is showing steady growth. In 2023, the share of the Republic of Korea in the total turnover of Uzbekistan was 3.7%. Since 2017, the volume of trade between countries has increased by 1.7 times, from \$ 1.4 billion to a record high of \$ 2.3 billion in 2023. This is evidenced by the stable interest and activation of

economic relations between Uzbekistan and South Korea (see table 1).

Table 1. Trade turnover between Uzbekistan and South Korea (USD million).

	2017	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Trade turnover	1 387 627	2 767 712	2 150 709	1 898 758	2 342 545	2 343 300
Import	1 244 288	2 664 821	2 099 372	1 841 057	2 299 780	2 302 900
Export	143 339	102 891	51 338	57 701	42 765	40 400
Trade balance	-1 100 949	-2 561 929	-2 048 034	-1 783 355	-2 257 015	-2 262 500

Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, https://stat.uz/img/press_reliz_tashi_savdo_eng_yanvar_dekabr_20_12-engokok.pdf

Analyzing the dynamics of the bilateral trade indicators between South Korea and Uzbekistan in the recent years, one can notice decreasing trend in the export indicators.

The major traded goods between the two countries highlight the complementary nature of their economies. Uzbekistan exports raw materials and agricultural products, while South Korea exports high-tech goods and machinery. An investigation of the structure of the trade turnover between South Korea and Uzbekistan can be founded in the following table.

Table 2. Structural analysis of the trade turnover between South Korea and Uzbekistan (USD millions).

	Import	Export
Consumption goods	6,7	4,4
Non consumption goods (excluding oil)	7,9	6,3
Petroleum	18,1	2,8
Chemical substances	282,9	0,6
Industrial goods	209,6	3,5
Machinery and equipment	1516,0	0,4
Retail goods	170,2	0,2
Services	91,6	22,4

Source: <https://review.uz/uz/post/infografika-ozbekistonning-janubiy-koreya-bilan-savdosi>

The analysis of the statistics on bilateral trade among countries indicate strong demand for Korean products such as cars, equipment, and electronics in the Uzbek market. On the other hand, Uzbekistan's export structure, services, mineral fuel, wood and wood products, textiles, and food products are prominent. The main imports of Uzbekistan consist of vehicles, spare parts, mechanical, and electrical equipment.

Considering the import structure and geography of the Uzbekistan, in the recent years during the reporting period, imports amounted to 38 141.2 million US dollars (the increase in growth rates compared to January-December 2022 was 24.0%). The main share in its structure is occupied by machinery and transport equipment (39.2%), industrial goods (16.6%), as well as chemicals and similar products (12.8%).

In general, based on the results of January-December 2023, goods and services were imported into Uzbekistan from 179 countries. More than 2/3 of imports come from such large partner countries as China, Russia, Kazakhstan, the Republic of Korea, Türkiye, Germany and Turkmenistan.

Figure 2. Top-eight partner countries in import for Republic of Uzbekistan.

Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, https://stat.uz/img/press_reliz_tashi_savdo_eng_yanvar_dekabr_20_12-engokok.pdf

II. Cooperation in the field of investments

Building upon trade relations, economic cooperation has crystallized as a foundational element of the bilateral relationship, propelled by shared interests in trade, investment, and technological exchange. South Korea’s sophisticated technology and robust investment capabilities synergize with Uzbekistan’s abundant natural resources and strategic Central Asian location. This collaborative dynamic has cul-

tivated a vibrant economic partnership, contributing to the developmental trajectories of both nations (Dadabaev T., 2018).

Numerous investment projects have been realized through this cooperative framework, with a particular emphasis on enhancing Uzbekistan's social infrastructure. Notable among these projects is the establishment of the Himchan Hospital in Bukhara in 2019, a \$7 million investment by the Korea Medical Foundation Sangwon that generated 140 local jobs. Additionally, in the same year, South Korea's Exim Bank spearheaded a \$18 million National e-Library project for Uzbekistan, digitizing 6 million books across 200 libraries nationwide.

The bilateral relationship between Uzbekistan and South Korea was further solidified in 2020 with the inauguration of the National Children's Hospital in Tashkent. This \$130.6 million project, with \$102.8 million contributed by South Korea, created 950 jobs and brought a 280-bed facility into operation. In the same year, Korea's Exim Bank contributed to the further development of the education sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Continuing its educational support, Korea's Exim Bank in 2020 facilitated the distribution of 45,936 computers to 2,766 comprehensive schools in Uzbekistan, investing \$14.4 million in a project totaling \$18 million (Embassy of the Republic of Uzbekistan to South Korea. <https://korea.mfa.uz/page/469>).

The third joint project between South Korea and Republic of Uzbekistan implemented in 2020 is aimed **at the facilitation of medical centers of Uzbekistan with modern equipment. Within the framework of the joint project,** 140 variety of the medical equipment have been provided to

187 regional medical centers in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Following a brief hiatus in joint project implementation from 2021 to 2023, Uzbekistan and South Korea rekindled their bilateral cooperation in December 2023 with the establishment of the Tashkent Pharma Park. This \$160 million project, with a \$135.8 million contribution from South Korea, represents one of the largest joint investments. It includes the establishment of a Pharmaceutical Technical University and research center, aimed at nurturing highly skilled professionals in pharmaceuticals, medical equipment, cosmetology, and related fields (Rakhimov M., 2022).

The opening of the first Trade House of Uzbekistan in Seoul in March 2024 signified a significant advancement in the economic partnership between Uzbekistan and South Korea. This milestone is expected to serve as a pivotal platform for promoting Uzbek goods and services in the South Korean market, fostering robust business connections, and boosting exports to South Korea. This initiative is poised to reinforce and fortify the economic bonds between the two countries.

In collaboration with South Korea, Uzbekistan has established a range of joint ventures, including a state-of-the-art textile technology park, a cutting-edge Scientific and Technological Centre for Rare Metals and Alloys, a pioneering Design and Technological Centre for Agricultural Machinery, and the groundbreaking Uzbek-Korean Centre for Cooperation in Electronic Government (Dunyo IA, 2024). Furthermore, South Korea has lent vital support to the launch of the National E-Commerce Platform in Uzbekistan.

For Uzbekistan, promising areas of economic cooperation include expanding cooperation in the energy, oil and gas, chemical, mining, transport and logistics sectors, implementing new projects in mechanical and electrical engineering, the textile and food industries, and infrastructure development. Uzbekistan is also interested in developing free economic zones modeled after successful Korean experiences, creating joint ventures in leading economic sectors, and implementing innovative projects. To this end, in 2019, Uzbekistan and Korea signed agreements on transferring the Angren economic zone to the Incheon free economic zone trust and establishing the production of essential medicines in the Bustonlik-farm industrial zone in the Tashkent region. The priority direction of the Uzbek-Korean partnership also includes agreements on intensifying bilateral cooperation within the process of Uzbekistan's entrance to the World Trade Organization through expert consultation.

III. Development assistance to republic of Uzbekistan

The economic ties between South Korea and Uzbekistan also encompass the provision of developmental assistance. South Korea has transitioned from a recipient of Official Development Assistance (ODA) to a substantial donor since 1987. By 2010, it had become a member of the OECD's Development Assistance Committee (DAC), cementing its position in the global aid landscape. According to OECD data from 2024, South Korea's ODA had reached approximately \$2.79 billion, constituting 0.17% of its Gross National Income (OECD, 2024).

Figure 3. Bilateral Official development assistance provided by South Korea to Uzbekistan.

Source: OECD (2024), “Korea”, in Development Co-operation Profiles, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/d919ff1a-en> (accessed on 18 September 2024).

Although Uzbekistan did not rank among the top-ten recipients of South Korean ODA in 2022, it was the 8th largest beneficiary of Korean foreign aid in 2020. The volume of aid has shown variability over the years, peaking at 40 million USD in 2022.

The Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA), established in 1991, is the principal entity overseeing South Korea’s foreign aid initiatives. KOICA executes the government’s ODA programs, with a focus on optimizing grant aid to developing nations. The agency’s primary emphasis is on technical assistance, including the provision of equipment and technologies, training of specialists in premier Korean institutions, and the deployment of Korean experts and volunteers to developing countries.

Since the inception of the KOICA Uzbekistan office in 1995, it has facilitated 28 development projects. These projects are in line with the country partnership strategy (2016-2020) and the national development plan (2017-2021). The primary focus areas of KOICA's projects in Uzbekistan include Education, Health, Water Management, and Public Administration (KOICA Uzbekistan,2024).

Additionally, the KOICA Uzbekistan Office has hosted 2,100 trainees in Korea for diverse training programs. These initiatives aim to enhance technical skills and knowledge, with a focus on capacity-building for sustainable socio-economic development. Graduates of these programs have assumed key roles in their respective fields, contributing significantly as human resources leaders in Uzbek society. Notably, among the KOICA program trainees, there have been 140 public sector officials from Uzbekistan (<https://korea.mfa.uz/page/469?language=ru>).

Furthermore, KOICA has a project entitled “World Friends Korea” which focuses on bringing Korean experts and specialist to the relevant sectors. Up to the date, KOICA Uzbekistan Office has sent out over 500 overseas volunteers in the fields of Korean Language, Computer Technology, Taekwondo, Health, and Child Education (<http://www.worldfriend-skorea.or.kr/eng/>).

IV. Cooperation in the field of labor migration

Economic cooperation between South Korea and Uzbekistan extends to the sphere of labor migration between the two nations. In recent years, labor migration from Uzbeki-

stan to South Korea has surged significantly, supported by various initiatives introduced by the South Korean government. One such initiative is the Employment Permit System (EPS), designed to address labor shortages in sectors such as manufacturing and agriculture by allowing foreign workers to legally enter the South Korean labor market. This migration yields mutual benefits: it supports Uzbek workers and their families through remittances, while simultaneously aiding South Korea's economy by meeting labor demand in critical sectors.

According to the Immigration Office of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Korea, as of March 2024, 89,902 Uzbek nationals were residing in South Korea, representing 3.5% of the country's total foreign population of 2,594,936. This marks an increase of approximately 9.3% from March 2023, when the figure stood at 81,567 Uzbek nationals.

Furthermore, as of March 2024, 56,408 Uzbek migrants held residence permits, constituting 62.7% of all Uzbek migrants in South Korea—an increase of nearly 11% compared to March 2023 (50,351 individuals). In contrast, the number of Uzbek migrants holding short-term permits decreased by 3.2%, with 5,716 individuals in March 2024, compared to 5,903 in March 2023. Additionally, the number of ethnic Koreans holding Uzbek nationality reached 43,335 individuals as of March 2024, accounting for 48.2% of the Uzbek migrant population. This represents a substantial growth of nearly 18% from March 2023 (International Organization for Migration. Uzbekistan — Migration Situation Report. 2024).

Figure 4. Number of Uzbek migrants living in the Republic of Korea, 2023-2024 (absolute numbers) Uzbekistan — Migration Situation Report. Quarterly Compilation (Jan-Mar 2024).

<https://dtm.iom.int/reports/uzbekistan-migration-situation-report-quarterly-Compilation-jan-mar-2024>

V. Ecological aspects of partnership between South Korea and Uzbekistan in the context of sustainable development

Environmental sustainability has become a global priority, urging nations to collaborate on critical ecological issues. The Republic of Korea and Uzbekistan, two influential players in their respective regions, have increasingly focused on strengthening their bilateral cooperation in promoting environmental sustainability. South Korea’s advanced technologies and green growth strategies provide valuable expertise, while Uzbekistan’s growing economy and vast natural resources create unique opportunities for such collaboration. Both countries are actively engaged in joint environmental

projects aimed at improving ecological conditions and addressing climate change.

A key focus of this partnership is the implementation of advanced water and air purification technologies. South Korean experts and companies are supporting Uzbekistan in adopting modern waste treatment and recycling techniques, thereby contributing to the enhancement of the country's environmental quality.

One notable example of this cooperation is the ecological agreement signed between the governments of South Korea and Uzbekistan. This agreement was followed by the establishment of a representative office of the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) in Uzbekistan and the participation of the Uzbek delegation in the Global Green Hub events in Busan. These initiatives signify a growing commitment to ecological collaboration between the two nations.

Beyond these recognized priorities, several other areas offer substantial opportunities for deepened cooperation:

a) Renewable Energy Development.

Uzbekistan has considerable potential for renewable energy, particularly in solar and wind power, given its abundant sunshine and expansive open landscapes. South Korea's expertise in renewable energy technologies, such as photovoltaic systems and wind turbines, can support Uzbekistan in diversifying its energy sources. Collaborative efforts in this area would not only reduce Uzbekistan's reliance on fossil fuels but also lower greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with global climate change mitigation strategies.

The Uzbek government aims to increase its renewable energy capacity to 25 GW by 2030, with 40% of the nation's

electricity to be generated from renewable sources. This goal is central to Uzbekistan's broader energy transition strategy, designed to meet the growing energy needs of its economy and population. South Korean firms, such as Tae-Chang NET Co., Ltd., are well-positioned to assist in this transformation by modernizing Uzbekistan's renewable energy infrastructure. Tae-Chang NET has committed to upgrading five hydroelectric power plants in the Tashkent and Samarkand regions, contributing significantly to Uzbekistan's energy sustainability.

b) Water Resource Management.

Water scarcity is a pressing environmental challenge in Uzbekistan, particularly in regions such as the Aral Sea basin. South Korea's experience with cutting-edge water management technologies—including desalination, water recycling, and efficient irrigation techniques - can substantially improve Uzbekistan's water security. Collaborative efforts in this domain will not only promote sustainable agricultural practices but also contribute to the rehabilitation of ecosystems in drought-prone areas. South Korea's expertise in smart water management could prove essential in addressing Uzbekistan's acute water shortages.

c) Air Quality Improvement.

Both South Korea and Uzbekistan face significant air quality challenges. In South Korea, rapid urbanization has exacerbated pollution levels, while Uzbekistan's industrial activities continue to impact air quality negatively. Joint initiatives could focus on reducing industrial emissions, promoting the use of cleaner energy sources, and enhancing air quality monitoring systems. South Korea's success in pollution

reduction through the implementation of stringent regulations and green technologies provides a valuable model for Uzbekistan to follow.

d) Waste Management and Recycling.

As Uzbekistan's urban population continues to expand, waste management has become a critical concern. South Korea's efficient waste management system, which prioritizes recycling, waste-to-energy technologies, and the reduction of plastic waste, offers a practical solution to Uzbekistan's growing waste disposal issues. By adopting South Korea's model, Uzbekistan can address its waste management challenges while simultaneously creating new green industries and employment opportunities.

In 2023, South Korea and Uzbekistan initiated a joint project to improve solid waste management in the Jizzakh region. This project, titled "Integrated Waste Management in the Jizzakh Region," is expected to be funded by the South Korean government's Economic Development and Cooperation Fund (EDCF). The initiative underscores the importance of sustainable waste management in Uzbekistan's urban planning strategies.

e) Smart Cities and Sustainable Urban Planning.

As a global leader in smart city development, South Korea's ability to integrate technology into urban planning to optimize resource use and reduce environmental impact offers significant benefits for Uzbekistan's rapidly growing cities. Uzbekistan's urban centers, including Tashkent and Samarkand, stand to gain from South Korea's experience in implementing smart infrastructure, clean transportation systems, and energy-efficient buildings. These developments would not only enhance the resilience of Uzbekistan's cities

to climate change but also better equip them to manage rapid population growth.

VI. Multilateral cooperation

Alongside the strategic partnership in the bilateral level, Uzbekistan and South Korea have established an effective platform for the development of a multilateral format of cooperation. For instance, within the framework of cooperation in the international arena, Seoul supported and co-sponsored resolutions adopted at the initiative of Uzbekistan by the UN General Assembly: “Strengthening regional and international cooperation to ensure peace, stability and sustainable development in the Central Asian region” and “Education and religious tolerance” (2018), “Sustainable tourism and sustainable development in Central Asia” (2019), “On strengthening the role of parliaments in accelerating the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals” (2022).

The South Korean side supported Uzbekistan’s candidacy to the UN Human Rights Council for 2021-2023, as well as Samarkand’s candidacy to host the 25th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) in 2023.

The partnership between South Korea and Uzbekistan in the domain of environmental sustainability holds great potential for addressing key ecological challenges. By leveraging South Korea’s technological advancements and Uzbekistan’s natural resources, the two nations can make significant strides toward achieving sustainable development goals. Key areas of collaboration, including renewable energy, water management, air quality improvement, waste management, and smart city development, form the foundation of this part-

nership. This collaboration not only benefits the ecological development of both countries but also contributes to broader regional and global environmental objectives.

First Deputy Director of the Institute for Strategic and Interregional Studies under the President of Uzbekistan, Akramjon Nematov, emphasized the importance of deepening cooperation between Central Asia and South Korea during his speech at the Forum of Central Asian and Korean Think Tanks in Tashkent (Dunyo IA, July 30, 2024). According to Nematov, Central Asian countries and South Korea hold significant potential to become key participants in the emerging global architecture of value chains. He highlighted the need to fully understand and seize the opportunities for mutually beneficial collaboration.

Central Asia, with a population of 80 million people, is rapidly growing both economically and demographically. It is projected that by 2050, the average age of the population will be 30 years, making it one of the youngest regions globally. Furthermore, the region's educational standards are improving substantially, which opens new avenues for collaboration with South Korea. Central Asian countries are rich not only in energy resources but also in strategically important minerals such as molybdenum, lithium, and cobalt, which are critical for the development of high-tech industries and the transition to a green economy.

The political consolidation of Central Asian states enhances their collective efforts in industrial cooperation and the development of key transportation corridors, such as the "North-South" and "East-West" routes, positioning the region as an important economic hub. Over the past decade, the region's economy has grown by 6% annually, significantly outpacing global averages. These growth rates are

expected to continue, especially in the industrial and manufacturing sectors.

In recent years, the region has also experienced a doubling of external trade volumes, with intra-regional trade increasing more than fourfold. A significant factor has been the growing influx of investments, which has increased by 1.5 times since 2016, reaching \$50 billion in 2022.

The geostrategic location of Central Asia in the heart of Eurasia is another critical asset. Combined with a policy of openness and balanced relations with external partners, this makes the region a pivotal trans-regional transport, logistics, and production hub within the global economy, fostering an environment of mutually beneficial cooperation based on healthy competition.

In June 2024, the South Korea's government unveiled the K-Silk Road Initiative, aimed at strengthening partnerships with Central Asia across four key areas: resource development, official development assistance, people-to-people exchange and public-private networking (Lee Hyo-jin, 2024).

Developing industrial cooperation through the transfer of South Korean technologies—this will create opportunities for joint production and entry into new markets with high value-added products. Combining Central Asia's human capital and natural resources with South Korean technologies will enable both regions to enter third-country markets with highly competitive products. This strategic framework offers numerous advantages for both Korea and the countries in the region. Korea pursues bilateral and multilateral relations with a win-win approach, circumventing regional tensions. This stance shows Korea's commitment to supporting mutually beneficial partnerships in Central Asia through the "K-Silk Road" initiative (Mehmet Fatih Oztarsu, 2024).

VII. Perspectives and priority areas of future collaboration between South Korea and Uzbekistan

The cooperation between the Republic of Korea and Uzbekistan encompasses various sectors, emphasizing economic growth, technological advancement, and educational development. Both nations are committed to enhancing bilateral relations through initiatives such as advanced science and technology hubs, water and air purification technologies, and educational exchanges. This multifaceted partnership aims to foster long-term collaboration, positioning Uzbekistan as a key player in Central Asia for South Korea's strategic interests (Fumagalli. M, 2016). The ongoing efforts reflect a shared vision for sustainable development and mutual prosperity.

The pathway of the strategic cooperation between Uzbekistan and South Korea for the following years have been paved during the recent visit at the presidential level. In June 2024 President Yoon Suk Yeol of the Republic of Korea conducted a state visit to Uzbekistan. The visit marked a pivotal moment in the bilateral relations between the two nations, as high-level talks were held in Tashkent to discuss the advancement of Uzbek-Korean relations. Central to these discussions was the enhancement of the special strategic partnership between the countries, with a focus on expanding practical cooperation in various sectors such as trade, innovation, energy, and infrastructure. President Mirziyoyev heralded a new era of high-tech and innovative cooperation, announcing plans to establish a regional high-tech hub in Uzbekistan. This initiative aims to focus on critical sectors such as raw materials processing, semiconductors, smart agriculture, and green energy (Daryo IA, 2024).

During the visit, leaders of the states identified sev-

eral critical sectors for future collaboration as an anchors for the continued growth of the Uzbek-Korean partnership over the next three years.

Mineral Resources. A key aspect of the economic partnership is the development of Uzbekistan's critical mineral resources. The strategic framework emphasizes the deep processing of the country's resource base to establish a comprehensive value chain—from extraction to final production. This approach aims to maximize resource efficiency, enhance sustainability, and bolster Uzbekistan's role in the global minerals market.

Semiconductor industry. Recognizing South Korea's global leadership in the semiconductor sector, bilateral cooperation in this field has been prioritized. Plans are underway to establish Uzbekistan's first fully integrated research and production cluster for semiconductor products. This initiative is expected to position Uzbekistan as a regional hub for semiconductor manufacturing, leveraging South Korean expertise and technological advancements.

Chemical Industry and Green Hydrogen Production. The chemical industry presents significant opportunities for collaboration, particularly in the production of green hydrogen and ammonia, as well as rubber manufacturing. These initiatives align with international sustainability efforts aimed at reducing carbon emissions and fostering the transition to a green economy. The development of green hydrogen projects supports Uzbekistan's long-term energy security goals and contributes to global decarbonization efforts.

Engineering and Automotive Industry. The engineering and automotive sectors have witnessed tangible progress, highlighted by the recent launch of a KIA car assembly line in Uzbekistan's Jizzakh region. Expansion plans include full-

scale production of sedans, with an expected annual capacity exceeding 60,000 units by next year. This collaboration underscores the growing industrial integration between the two nations and enhances Uzbekistan's manufacturing capabilities.

Smart Agriculture and Technology Transfer. Another key area of focus is the transfer of advanced technologies to Uzbekistan's agricultural sector. The introduction of "smart" and "green" technologies, along with the digitalization of agricultural processes, is expected to significantly enhance productivity and sustainability. Agreements have been reached to establish modern greenhouse farms and orchard complexes powered by renewable energy, reinforcing Uzbekistan's commitment to sustainable agricultural practices.

Infrastructure Modernization and Urban Development. Korean financial institutions and enterprises have shown strong interest in modernizing Uzbekistan's transport infrastructure and supporting residential and commercial real estate projects through public-private partnerships. These initiatives aim to enhance urban development, improve public services, and foster economic growth by integrating modern infrastructure solutions.

Energy Efficiency and Green Energy Initiatives. The advancement of green energy projects and energy efficiency programs forms a crucial pillar of bilateral cooperation. Both governments have agreed to resume strategic discussions at the ministerial level, particularly focusing on renewable energy projects. The ongoing collaboration with the Korea Eximbank and the Economic Development Cooperation Fund (EDCF) has already resulted in joint projects worth over \$3

billion, demonstrating the scale of commitment to sustainable energy development.

Financial Commitments and New Projects. South Korea upgraded the basic agreement on the Economic Development Cooperation Fund to double the upper limit to \$2 billion for the 2024-27 period to support development projects. The increased funding will aid in the second phase of constructing a pharmaceutical cluster at Tashkent Pharmaceutical University for drug development research and clinical trials. (The Korea Times, 2024). Overall, a new project portfolio valued at \$9.6 billion has been established, reflecting the ambitious scale of economic collaboration in the coming years.

The identified priority areas - ranging from mineral resources and semiconductors to green energy and smart agriculture - offer significant prospects for mutual economic growth, technological advancement, and environmental sustainability.

Conclusion

The partnership between South Korea and Uzbekistan presents vast opportunities for both nations. By leveraging South Korea's technological expertise and Uzbekistan's natural resources, the two countries can address pressing environmental challenges while promoting sustainable development. Key sectors such as renewable energy, water management, air quality, waste management, ecotourism and smart urban planning offer fertile ground for cooperation. This partnership not only benefits the two nations but also contributes to regional stability and global environmen-

tal objectives. As Tashkent and Seoul continue to explore new areas for collaboration, including the green economy, digitalization, and innovation, the Uzbek-South Korean relationship, established in 1992, stands as a model of strategic cooperation poised for further expansion.

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KEY DIRECTIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND SOUTH KOREA COLLABORATION IN THE SOCIAL SPHERE

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Uzbekistan and South Korea established diplomatic relations on January 29, 1992, setting a precedent for successful cooperation across multiple domains. Over the span of 30 years, the bilateral relationship has significantly developed, passing through several critical stages. In 2006, a Joint Declaration on Strategic Partnership was signed, and by 2019, the partnership had evolved into a “special strategic partnership.” [Между Узбекистаном и Южной Кореей подписаны...]

In June 2024, during the signing of a statement aimed at expanding this special partnership, the presidents of both nations reached agreements in the areas of science, education, healthcare, and labor relations. These agreements include a contract with the Export-Import Bank of Korea to supply equipment for scientific and ICT education in schools, cooperation to enhance the capacity of Uzbekistan’s civil servants, a memorandum on training qualified professionals, and an agreement to implement an innovative pharmaceutical cluster project called “Pharma Park.”

1.1. Science and Education

Uzbekistan’s higher education institutions maintain active cooperation with more than 45 universities and re-

search organizations from South Korea. Four South Korean university branches operate in Uzbekistan, including Inha, Puchon, and Yeosu in Tashkent, and the Korean International University in Fergana. These institutions offer diverse academic programs. [Embassy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the United Kingdom...] For instance, Inha University's Tashkent branch, opened in 2014, specializes in computer science and high technology, with all courses delivered in English. Yeosu Technical Institute, which opened in 2018 as Uzbekistan's first private university, provides courses in fields like architecture, urban planning, civil engineering, alternative energy, business management, tourism, international marketing, and Korean language philology. [Contributors to Wikimedia projects...]

Additionally, Uzbek students have the opportunity to study in South Korea's leading universities, with around 7,500 Uzbek students enrolled as of 2019. Scientific exchanges and joint research in areas such as IT, medicine, and engineering contribute to the growth of both nations' scientific potential. In March 2023, the Forum of Rectors, which brought together representatives from top universities of both countries, was held in Tashkent.

These new initiatives in education and technology illustrate a long-term, comprehensive partnership aimed at human capital development and accelerating innovation. During talks between President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan and President Yoon Suk-Yeol of South Korea, agreements were made on a three-year strategic program to create a high-tech hub in Uzbekistan. The key areas of collaboration include automotive development, the creation of the region's first fully operational semiconductor production cluster,

smart agriculture implementation, infrastructure modernization, and advancing green energy projects.

As part of these efforts, a memorandum of understanding was signed between Samarkand International University of Technology and Seongnam Industrial Complex Corporation during the summit, reflecting the broad scope of collaboration.

The study of the Korean language is available in 13 universities, 48 schools, and lyceums across Uzbekistan. Conversely, Uzbek language departments have been established at South Korean universities of foreign languages in the cities of Busan and Daegu. The total number of Uzbek students in South Korean universities exceeds 20,000, facilitated by the effective preparation of Uzbek nationals through vocational training centers in Tashkent, Samarkand, Shakhrisabz, Fergana, and Urgench, established with the support of KOICA. Since 1992, the Korean Education Centre in Tashkent has been offering competitive language internships in South Korea, as well as professional development courses for university professors and students. Korean language and culture centres are also active in institutions like the Uzbek State University of World Languages, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, and the University of World Economy and Diplomacy.

Since 1995, over 150 information technology teachers from Tashkent's educational institutions have improved their qualifications in South Korea under a cooperation agreement between the Tashkent Department of Public Education and the Seoul Department of Education.

Scientific cooperation between Uzbekistan and South Korea is rapidly advancing through joint research in areas such

as biotechnology, nanotechnology, medical sciences, agriculture, and ecology. Research institutes and universities from both nations collaborate on joint projects and academic exchanges, fostering scientific growth and innovation. These initiatives are pivotal in accelerating scientific progress and the integration of advanced technologies into the economy and society.

A notable example of fruitful collaboration is the partnership between South Korea's Daegu Haany University (DHU) and the Bukhara State Medical Institute. Bilateral efforts in knowledge and experience exchange have significantly enhanced existing capacities. According to an ongoing agreement, there is active work on advancing traditional medicine, including the construction of "smart" greenhouses at the Bukhara State Medical Institute for growing medicinal plants. Additionally, a cluster for the production of pharmaceuticals and cosmetics is being developed.

It is worth noting that DHU plans to expand its cooperation with the Bukhara State Medical Institute by creating a research and production facility focused on traditional medicine and training Uzbek youth in pharmaceuticals. There are also plans to establish a King Sejong University. [Узбекистан – Южная Корея: новое время...]

In collaboration with South Korea, Uzbekistan has created a joint educational and practical textile technopark, a Scientific and Technological Centre for Rare Metals and Alloys, a Design and Technological Centre for Agricultural Machinery, and the Uzbek-Korean Cooperation Centre for e-Government.

Looking ahead, there are plans to launch a new joint educational program between Turin Polytechnic University in

Tashkent and South Korea's Yeungnam University. It is anticipated that this partnership will expand under the "2+2" program. The presidents of both countries have also endorsed proposals to establish an institute in Uzbekistan based on the model of the Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST). [Узбекистан и Корея: сотрудничество в сфере образования...]

1.2. Healthcare

The healthcare sector is a key priority area of cooperation. With financial and technical support from the Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA), Uzbek specialists have been enhancing their qualifications in leading clinics and centres in South Korea, while South Korean doctors have been providing free medical examinations for residents of Uzbekistan.

Healthcare cooperation has been steadily growing. South Korea facilitates the training and internships of Uzbek healthcare workers in top Korean clinics and centres. Under KOICA's volunteer program, more than 30 South Korean volunteers have worked in medical institutions across Uzbekistan. [Узбекистан и Корея: сотрудничество в сфере образования...]

In 2018, joint medical examinations and free surgeries were conducted for the population with the participation of South Korean specialists, including those from Vision Care (858 people), the Siloam Centre for the Blind, Sejong Hospital (36 children), Yonsei University, Inha University (922 people), Bundang University (about 100 people), Ewha Womans University (1,059 people), and Chong Hospital (3,622 people).

A government-level healthcare agreement signed during the state visit of Uzbekistan's president to South Korea from December 16-18, 2021, marked a new phase in bilateral cooperation. On October 22, 2022, the Ministry of Health announced that Uzbekistan would collaborate with South Korea on disease prevention and control, following a presidential decree issued on October 20, approving an international agreement on this partnership.

In 2020, with the assistance of the EDCF Fund, a multi-profile children's medical centre was completed in Tashkent. This successful project laid the foundation for a larger initiative to construct a medical cluster, which will include an adult hospital, an oncology clinic, a medical university, and a pharmaceutical cluster. In 2019, plans were initiated to create a national multi-profile surgical clinic (Level IV) for adult patients, with an estimated investment of \$150 million. In April 2019, the Uzbek-Korean Healthcare Cooperation Centre was established, and the first Uzbek-Korean e-healthcare forum took place in Tashkent in September 2019. [Embassy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the United Kingdom...]

Under a tripartite agreement signed in September 2010 between Uzbekistan's Ministry of Health, Inha University Hospital, and the Healthy Generation Foundation, 8,430 patients were treated by Inha University Hospital specialists between 2010 and 2018, with 10 of them receiving surgery in South Korean clinics. [Узбекистан и Южная Корея укрепляют сотрудничество в области народной медицины...]

From 2014 to 2018, Vision Care ophthalmologists, supported by POSCO DAEWOO, conducted medical examinations for 5,699 individuals in multi-profile medical centres

in Bukhara and Fergana regions, performing cataract removal and lens replacement surgeries for 848 patients as donations.

Under another tripartite agreement between Uzbekistan's Ministry of Health, JCI Korea, Bundang CHA Hospital, and the Healthy Generation Foundation, 275 patients with heart diseases were examined at the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute between 2009 and 2019, and 87 children were successfully operated on in South Korean clinics with donor funding.

Several healthcare projects are currently being implemented with South Korea's support. A notable project involves the construction of a National Children's Medical Centre in Tashkent by the Baum Corporation, with an investment exceeding \$130 million. Various ongoing projects, supported by the Korea Foundation for International Healthcare (KOFIH), focus on key areas such as healthcare, medical staff training, and diagnostic improvement. [Oliy Majlis Senati...]

During the 2024 talks between the presidents of South Korea and Uzbekistan, an agreement was reached to accelerate the development and implementation of a medical cluster that includes a university, an adult hospital, and an oncology clinic. Additionally, a long-term program for training Uzbek healthcare professionals in specialized centres in South Korea will be launched.

1.3. Labor Relations

On August 16, 2003, South Korea enacted the "Employment of Foreign Workers Act," which introduced the Employment Permit System (EPS) for foreign workers alongside the

existing system for industrial training. This system, implemented in 2004, allowed foreign workers to be employed freely in specific sectors. As of 2018, 16 countries, including Uzbekistan, participate in the EPS, facilitating legal employment for their citizens in South Korea. [Узбекистан и Республика Корея будут укреплять сотрудничество в сфере трудовых отношений...]

In 2024, following “complex negotiations,” Uzbekistan reached an agreement with South Korean authorities to allow Uzbek nationals to participate in seasonal work programs. In 2021, South Korea temporarily suspended the recruitment of Uzbek workers due to widespread violations of employment contracts, where many Uzbeks overstayed their visas. [Embassy of the Republic of Korea in the Republic of Uzbekistan...] However, as part of the 2024 agreement, 100,000 Uzbek citizens will be eligible to compete for jobs in South Korea, with an initial phase offering more than 37,000 positions. [Корея увеличила для граждан Узбекистана...]

In response to the growing demand for skilled labour migration, an office of Uzbekistan’s Agency for External Labor Migration has been established in Gwangju, South Korea. This office facilitates communication between labour authorities in both countries and assists Uzbek workers in navigating employment opportunities.

In addition, Uzbekistan is exploring a partnership with the Korean Institute of Public Administration and the National Human Resources Development Institute to establish a Digital Technology and Artificial Intelligence Training Centre at the Academy of Public Administration in Tashkent. This centre aims to enhance the skills of Uzbek professionals in

cutting-edge technologies, improving their global competitiveness.

The South Korean side has expressed interest in attracting Uzbek workers to the automobile servicing sector. According to Kwak Yong Chhol, Chairman of the Korea Automobile Manufacturers Association, South Korea has an annual demand for approximately 3,000 workers in the automotive industry. Currently, 48,000 employees work across 6,800 automotive enterprises in South Korea. [3,000 Uzbek Citizens...]

The importance of expanding organized labour migration programs has been emphasized, with a focus on ensuring the protection of the labour and social rights of Uzbek citizens working abroad. There are also initiatives to support returning migrant workers by engaging them in entrepreneurial and labour activities within Uzbekistan, contributing to the nation's economic development.

Moreover, the Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA) continues to play a critical role in fostering vocational training in Uzbekistan. KOICA's programs aim to increase the competitiveness of Uzbek workers in both the domestic and international labour markets, providing them with the skills needed to meet global labour demands effectively. These collaborative efforts further strengthen the labour ties between Uzbekistan and South Korea, offering mutual benefits in terms of employment, skill development, and economic growth.

1.4. Marriage

The historical relocation of Koreans to Uzbekistan, which occurred during Stalin's era, significantly shaped the diaspora's experience. Initially isolated from their homeland, the

Korean community maintained a connection to their cultural roots while adapting to the social and economic landscape of Central Asia. This dual identity allowed them to contribute to Uzbekistan's economy, particularly in agriculture and commerce, while also preserving elements of Korean culture such as language, traditions, and cuisine.

The Korean diaspora is one of the largest ethnic groups residing in Uzbekistan. As a result of political decisions and historical events, Koreans were forcibly relocated to Uzbekistan in 1937, dispersed across the country rather than settled in concentrated communities. Despite this, the Korean community has played an active role in the economic and cultural life of Central Asia, though it has faced strong cultural and linguistic influences from the surrounding ethnic groups. [*Casey, R., Koreans in Uzbekistan...*]

In South Korea, over 35 local governments have introduced special programs that offer marriage subsidies to local men who marry foreign brides. According to reports, a South Korean man spends an average of 18.3 million won (approximately \$22,000 USD) to marry a woman from Uzbekistan. These subsidies aim to address demographic challenges and encourage cross-cultural marriages. [*Pak L. V. On the study of the semantics of the wedding ceremony...*]

Over the past seven years, more than 20 Korean dramas have aired on Uzbek television, reflecting the growing cultural exchange between the two nations. In addition, the Sejong Korean Language School in Tashkent introduced a new course last year specifically designed for women who have entered into marriage with South Korean citizens. This course helps them integrate into South Korean society by teaching language skills and cultural knowledge.

In recent years, the increasing popularity of South Korean culture globally, particularly through K-dramas, K-pop, and Korean fashion, has bridged cultural gaps between the two nations. This influence has led to a growing interest in South Korea within Uzbekistan, as evidenced by the rise in Korean language courses and cultural exchanges. [Как живут межнациональные семьи в Узбекистане...]

Marriage programs and the integration of Uzbek women into South Korean society reflect a broader trend of cross-national unions. The support provided by South Korean municipalities indicates the importance of these marriages not only for the individuals involved but also for addressing broader demographic challenges. The Sejong Language School's initiative to train Uzbek brides in South Korean language and culture highlights the proactive measures taken to ensure smoother transitions and better integration for foreign spouses. [*Yakvalkhodjjeva, E., Uzbek Brides...*]

This growing interaction between Uzbekistan and South Korea, whether through cultural programs, marriages, or educational initiatives, signifies a deeper bond between the two nations, driven by shared interests in cultural exchange and mutual economic benefits.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan and South Korea's partnership has progressed significantly, driven by mutual goals in science, education, healthcare, and labour. Both countries are committed to deepening cooperation in innovation, human capital development, and strategic sectors, ensuring long-term mutual benefits.

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UZBEK-KOREAN RELATIONS IN THE SPHERE OF CULTURE

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Introduction

Uzbek-Korean cultural relations are distinguished by the spirit of cooperation and mutual respect. They strengthen ties between people and help deepen the understanding of each nation's cultural heritage. The Korean diaspora in the country has a great role in forming Uzbek-Korean culture. The presence of ethnic Koreans in Uzbekistan dates back to the 1930s when Koreans were deported from the Soviet Union to Central Asia. This created a unique cultural mix and shared history.

6.1. Relations of the Uzbek SSR and the DPRK in the sphere of culture in the Soviet period.

During the era of the Soviet Union, cultural ties between the Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic (Uzbek SSR) and the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK) were significantly shaped by the broader framework of Soviet cultural strategies and global diplomatic relations. The establishment of cultural connections between the Uzbek SSR and the DPRK primarily occurred through Soviet initiatives for cultural exchange, which were designed to foster socialist principles and solidarity among nations adhering to socialist ideologies.

As an integral part of the Soviet Union, the Uzbek SSR adhered to Soviet cultural policies that prioritized socialist realism and the advancement of Soviet cultural principles. This doctrinal influence extended to the realm of cultural exchanges with North Korea. Both regions engaged in cultural programs intended to champion socialist realism, an officially endorsed artistic style in the Soviet Union that underscored socialist values and realistic portrayals of ordinary life.

It is plausible that these cultural exchanges between the Uzbek SSR and the DPRK integrated propaganda components aimed at bolstering socialist doctrines and reinforcing the Soviet perspective. Nevertheless, comprehensive insight into the specific cultural connections and interactions between the Uzbek SSR and the DPRK during the Soviet period remains limited due to constrained access to information concerning North Korea's clandestine policies and cultural exchanges with other Soviet republics.

In essence, the cultural relations between the Uzbek SSR and the DPRK throughout the Soviet era evolved within

the framework of promoting socialist ideologies within the broader context of Soviet cultural policies, socialist realism, and international socialist solidarity. Notably, when exchanges between the Soviet Union and South Korea were interrupted, the translation and publication of Korean literature in Russian thrived due to interactions between North Korea and the Soviet Union. Although Korean literary works were primarily imported through North Korea, the majority of Korean literature was directly published by Soviet publishing houses. Consequently, the predominant body of Korean literary works released in the Soviet Union during this period can be attributed to the contributions of North Korean writers.

Research indicates that there are distinctive characteristics in the dissemination of Korean literature within the Russian-speaking domain compared to those prevalent in the 2000s. [Han, Seung-hee: 284] Notably, Korean literary works were predominantly published by a state-owned publishing entity in the Soviet Union during this time frame. Poetry genres were favored over novels, and it was common for the same author's works to be published multiple times by various publishers.

The distribution methods of Korean literature in the Soviet Union were categorized geographically into Russia, Central Asia, and Eastern Europe. Within Russia, publishing houses were situated in Moscow, St. Petersburg, the Far East, and Siberia. In the Central Asian region, publishing companies were established in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan.

Following Korea's independence in 1945, North Korea solidified diplomatic relations with the Soviet Union by signing a diplomatic treaty in 1946 and the North-Soviet Cultural Exchange Agreement in 1949. These agreements facilitated the

official introduction of Korean literary works to the Russian-speaking world through North Korea.

Starting from the early 1950s, significant works by prominent North Korean writers were published and introduced by Soviet publishers under the guise of cultural exchange. The publication statistics reveal that 52 works were released in the 1950s, 34 in the 1960s, 25 in the 1970s, 19 in the 1980s, and 18 in the 1990s. Notably, the majority of publications originated from the 1950s and 1960s, accounting for over two-thirds of the total output.

During the 1950s, there was a focus on publishing 38 contemporary literary works and 14 classics, primarily showcasing a select group of leading North Korean writers such as Lee Gi-yong, Han Seol-ya, Jo Gi-cheon, and Baek In-joon. These works often depicted scenes reflective of the wartime era, serving as a reflection of the Cold War dynamics between the USA and the Soviet Union. The delicate relationship between literary figures in the Soviet Union and North Korea, a Soviet satellite state, provided an opportunity for Soviet writers to engage with the literary creations of their North Korean counterparts. Publications from entities like the North Korean Cultural Propaganda Department, the new Chosun Publishing House, and the Foreign Language Literature Publishing House exhibited a balanced mix of classic and contemporary literature.

A noteworthy trend in the 1960s and 1970s was the increased volume of publications by publishing houses in Central Asia, particularly in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. Notably, in 1973, a collection of poems authored by Koryo-saram writers including Kim Jun, Myeong Dong-uk, Yang Man-chun, and Yelena Kim titled «Azaleas in the Meadow: Koryo Poets

of Kazakhstan» was published by the Kazakhstan Zazushy Publishing House (Жазушы), marking the first anthology dedicated to Koryo-saram works. [Han, Seung-Hee, 2017]

During the 1970s and 1980s, the prominent Nauka Publishing House (Наука) within the expansive Soviet Union played a significant role in disseminating a substantial amount of Korean literature. With the notable exception of Na Do-hyang and the anthology «Such People Lived: A Collection of Korean Short Stories» (Жили такие люди: Новеллы корейских писателей), the majority of these publications comprised classical literary works. [Choi, Ok-seon, 2004]

The Soviet Union, operating under a communist framework, faced formidable obstacles when it came to publishing foreign literature. The centralized Soviet publishing apparatus functioned on a planned basis, where books were meticulously produced and distributed according to predetermined quotas. Once a book fulfilled its allocation, it was typically not reprinted. The distinct processes of authorship, book production, and reader demand were compartmentalized, leading to a notable disparity between book supply and consumption, resulting in an inefficient system.

Given the unidirectional nature of the Soviet publishing system, which lacked a consumer-centric approach, determining the actual demand for Korean literature during that period based solely on publishing trends was impracticable. Nevertheless, considering that printing, publishing, and distribution were orchestrated under state supervision, it can be inferred that the publication of Korean literary works and their import from North Korea were largely dictated by policy imperatives.

Following the disintegration of the Soviet Union in the

1990s, the publishing landscape underwent a transformative phase catalyzed by Perestroika and Glasnost. Prior to the collapse of the Soviet Union, the enactment of the «Law on Publications and Other Mass Media» on June 12, 1990, marked a pivotal moment in Soviet history by abolishing censorship for the first time and guaranteeing press freedom.

State-owned publishing entities underwent privatization, leading to the emergence of numerous independent publishing houses and specialized publishers such as Giperion (Гиперион) focusing on specific genres like literature. By 2004, Russia boasted around 20,000 registered publishing companies, with approximately 7,000 consistently engaged in book publishing activities nationwide. This marked a substantial increase compared to the 202 publishing firms operating during the Soviet era, underscoring the significant evolution of the publishing industry in post-Soviet Russia.

Following the reestablishment of diplomatic ties between Korea and the Soviet Union in 1990, the trajectory of Korean literature dissemination in the Russian and Uzbek languages shifted towards South Korea rather than relying on North Korea's distribution network. Subsequently, with the establishment of the Literature Translation Institute of Korea in 2001, collaborative agreements and cultural exchanges between South Korean and Uzbek publishing entities have been actively pursued since the early 2000s.

Sporting interactions between Korea and the Soviet Union were initiated during the Fourth Republic of Korea in the 1970s. This period marked a phase of rapid economic progress in Korea, driven by the national ambition to portray a unified national identity that transcended the lingering effects of the Korean War through sports diplomacy. Consequently, a key objective within the sports domain was to

bolster national pride by attaining significant achievements on the global sports stage.

Throughout the *détente* era of the 1970s, sports engagements between Korea and the Soviet Union, under the leadership of the Brezhnev administration, steadily accrued a historical legacy, even amidst periods of non-diplomatic relations. By the 1980s, the policy of Northern Diplomacy in Korea and the reform initiatives and openness policies spearheaded by the Gorbachev administration in the latter stages of the Soviet era facilitated direct exchanges, notably revolving around the Seoul Olympics. [Kwon, Oh-In, 1988]

Consequently, the frequency of interactions, encompassing training sessions and amicable competitions, surged dramatically, leading to the establishment of structured and routine exchanges. Even within the realms of political and diplomatic analyses, sports engagements are acknowledged for their substantial role in kickstarting interactions with the communist bloc, notably the Soviet Union. [Kim, Mi-Sook, and Byung-Rok Song, 2013]

Moreover, within the framework of sporting interactions between Korea and the USSR, Soviet Korean athletes like Nelli Kim (women's artistic gymnastics, Belarus), Yuriy Tskhay (boxing, Kazakhstan), Vladimir Shin (boxing, Uzbekistan), and Vladimir Kim (weightlifting, Kyrgyzstan) played a crucial role in the advancement of Korean sports and the promotion of Korea-USSR sports exchanges post the Seoul Olympics. By assuming coaching roles for the South Korean national team as individuals of Soviet Korean descent, they actively facilitated civilian exchanges and contributed to the growth of sports engagements between the two nations. [Yoon, In-Jin, 2008]

The inaugural World Korean National Sports Festival took place from September 25 to October 4, 1989, in commem-

oration of the first anniversary of the Seoul Olympics. This gathering attracted over 1,420 individuals of Korean descent from 45 nations to engage in a variety of sports and cultural events. Notably, among the attendees were 150 Soviet Korean sports personalities, overseen by Vitaliy Pyen, the Deputy Minister of Sports of the Uzbek SSR, and Nellie Kim. This visit to South Korea marked a significant step towards formalizing discussions regarding Nellie Kim's potential appointment as the head coach of the South Korean women's gymnastics national team.

Subsequently, the second edition of the World Korean National Sports Festival occurred from September 11 to 20, 1991, boasting a larger and more diverse program than its predecessor. During this festival, Nellie Kim was invited as a distinguished speaker to deliver a lecture highlighting the achievements of Koreans as an ethnic minority in the Soviet Union. [Khodorovsky, Boris, 2011]

Before the Seoul Olympics, Yuriy Tskhay had garnered recognition in South Korea through his consistent engagement with the South Korean boxing delegation at international competitions since the early 1980s. According to Tskhay, by the commencement of the 1980s, Soviet Korean boxers had started to distinguish themselves with a unique style that set them apart from their Eastern European counterparts. Among the fifteen Soviet republics, four regions had Korean coaches overseeing their respective national boxing teams: Yuriy Tskhay in Kazakhstan, Vladimir Shin in Uzbekistan, Nikolai Lee in Russia, and Grigory Tsoi in Kyrgyzstan. Furthermore, several members of the Soviet national team, including Konstantin Tsyu and Felix Pak, were also of Korean descent. [Hwang, Yuseong, 1988]

The sports exchanges between Korea and the USSR can be

categorized into three distinct periods: the formative phase (1973-1984), the developmental phase (1985-1988.8), and the established phase (1988.9-1991). The defining characteristics of each phase are outlined as follows:

During the formative phase (1973-1984), South Korea's interactions with the Soviet Union were indirect, unilateral, lopsided, and confined, primarily revolving around involvement in international contests held within the Soviet Union. While these initial exchanges did not yield substantial outcomes, they facilitated Soviet Korean sports personalities in recognizing their ethnic heritage through engagements with South Korean athletes at global competitions.

Transitioning into the 1980s, marked by the hosting of the Asian Games and the Seoul Olympics, the Korea-USSR sports exchanges progressed into the developmental phase (1985-1988.8). The lead-up to the Seoul Olympics prompted a rapid surge in interactions, encompassing participation in international contests, training camps, and on-site adaptation sessions for athletes from both nations. Although these exchanges were still facilitated by intermediaries, the necessity for direct sports exchanges between the two countries was acknowledged, prompting visits by Soviet sports officials and the initiation of dialogues concerning formal sports exchange agreements.

After the successful culmination of the Seoul Olympics, the Korea-USSR sports exchanges progressed into the established phase (1988.9-1991), facilitating direct interactions between the two nations. These exchanges, involving the enlistment of Soviet coaches, training sessions, participation in global competitions, showcase matches, and friendly contests, notably propelled the quantitative and qualitative evolution of South Korea's sports domain.

Soviet Korean sports personalities like Nellie Kim and Yuriy Tskhay played pivotal roles in the Korea-USSR sports exchanges, contributing to the advancement of South Korean sports by adapting Soviet sports methodologies to the South Korean context. The significance of these exchanges can be delineated as follows: firstly, they set a precedent for international sports collaborations, offering a model for sporting interactions with other communist nations; secondly, the adaptation of Soviet sporting techniques in Korea laid the groundwork for enhancing South Korea's athletic prowess and capacities; thirdly, functioning as a facet of people-to-people diplomacy, these exchanges underscored the necessity for normalizing diplomatic ties between the two countries; and fourthly, the Seoul Olympics acted as a pivotal juncture that facilitated the normalization of relations between South Korea and the Soviet Union. [Yang, Mina, 2020]

During the period of sports exchanges between Korea and the USSR, people-to-people diplomacy played a significant role in fostering connections and understanding between individuals from both nations. The roles played by Soviet Korean sports figures, such as Nellie Kim and Yuriy Tskhay, are integral to this narrative. While it may be challenging to assert that these Soviet Koreans developed a transnational identity solely through their brief transnational sporting engagements, they were able to acknowledge their historical roots, establish connections, collaborate with sports personalities from both nations and gain insights into both cultures through these activities. This experience likely instigated a shift in their identity towards a transnational orientation.

However, just as these accomplishments were unfolding, the dissolution of the Soviet Union ushered in a new phase

in sports exchanges with the newly independent Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries.

6.2. Uzbek-Korean relations in the sphere of culture during the years of independence.

The historical connections between the populations of Uzbekistan and Central Asia with Korea date back to ancient times, exemplified by the presence of Korean envoys depicted on frescoes at the Afrasiab Museum in Samarkand. Through extensive periods of interaction and exchange, significant cultural and traditional advancements have emerged.

Following the attainment of independence, there has been a notable surge in cultural interactions between Uzbekistan and South Korea. These interactions have encompassed a diverse array of cultural manifestations, such as art exhibitions, musical performances, film screenings, and cultural festivals, serving to foster mutual comprehension and admiration of each other's cultural legacy.

The cultural exchange programs between Uzbekistan and Korea have played a crucial role in fostering understanding and cooperation between the two nations.

Presently, Uzbekistan and South Korea have acquired substantial expertise in advancing collaboration within the realms of culture and humanitarian affairs. The Uzbekistan–Republic of Korea Friendship Society has been in operation since 1999. To safeguard and enhance the spiritual and cultural legacy of the Korean populace, the Korean Government initiated the construction of the House of Korean Culture and Art in Tashkent. Strong inter-city relations have been established between Tashkent and Seoul, Fergana and Yongin, Namangan and Seongnam, Samarkand and Gyeo-

ngju, as well as the Tashkent region and Geongsangbuk-do province.

Furthermore, Seoul National Park was inaugurated on September 1, 2014, within the premises of «Babur» Park in Tashkent. Presently, ongoing construction efforts are focused on establishing the Korean House of Culture and Art. Annually, in collaboration with the Ministry of Cultural Affairs of Uzbekistan and the Embassy of the Republic of Korea in Uzbekistan, the country hosts the «Korean Culture Week.» This week-long event features a variety of activities including Korean film screenings, traditional Korean artist workshops, art and photography exhibitions, Korean song and speech competitions, as well as Korean fashion shows.

The creative industries, including arts and entertainment, have acted as a significant conduit between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea. Through captivating performances and stimulating exhibitions, this cultural interchange has sparked a revival of cultural appreciation, enabling the populations of both nations to celebrate the richness of each other's artistic expressions.

The artistic interchange between Uzbekistan and Korea commenced with the arrival of Korean diaspora artists in Korea. Noteworthy creations from this period include a series that portrays the suffering and mortality of the populace. Notable pieces from this collection, such as «The Ceremony of Separation» (1982), «Edo» (1982), «Discipline» (1982), and «Foundation» (1984), exemplify the significant shift from traditional to contemporary art, evident in their thematic depth and expressive techniques.

Transitioning into the contemporary era, the emphasis has shifted towards collaborative efforts and joint exhibitions between the two nations. For instance, in 2007, to com-

memorate the first anniversary of Shin Sun-nam's passing, an exhibition titled «Three Modern Artists from Uzbekistan» was hosted at the Han Ga-ram Art Museum. [Shin, Hyecho, 2021] Participation by artists like Shin Iskandar, Salim Rahmetov, and Sabir Akhmedov underscored the advancements and partnerships within the realm of contemporary art. Since the year 2000, the artistic exchange has made substantial strides through institutional collaborations and exhibitions. Notable among these exhibitions is «Korean Diaspora – Beyond Dispersion» which took place in 2018 at the Gyeonggi Museum of Modern Art, attracting considerable attention and earning high praise in the media. [Rakhimov M., 2022]

Esteemed artists like Kang Hee-soo, Rim Ra-na, and Kim Vladimir took part, demonstrating the deepening cultural connections between the respective nations. Korean cultural forms, encompassing cinema, animation, and music, have gained significant popularity across various generations within Central Asian communities. Cultural and humanitarian collaboration stands as a pivotal element for sustainable progress; however, it is imperative to persist in implementing effective measures to enhance mutual relationships, both in bilateral and multilateral contexts, thus bolstering the advancement of partnerships between South Korea and Central Asia. This partnership encompasses people-to-people interactions, educational initiatives, cultural exchanges, strategic diplomacy, and academic affiliations.

Since 1992-94, the Korean educational center has been operational in Tashkent. The center focuses on fostering Korean language acquisition through competitive programs in the Republic of Korea, as well as organizing professional development courses for university educators and students.

Presently, Korean language and cultural centers are op-

erational within the prominent higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan, including the State University of World Languages of Uzbekistan, the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, and the University of World Economy and Diplomacy. Korean language courses are integrated into the curricula of 12 universities and 28 schools and lyceums across the nation. Uzbek-Korean educational hubs were founded in Tashkent in 2012 and in Samarkand in 2016 through the sponsorship of the Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA).

Annually, in collaboration with the Ministry of Cultural Affairs of Uzbekistan and the Embassy of the Republic of Korea in Uzbekistan, the country hosts the «Korean Culture Week.» This event features a range of activities such as Korean film screenings, workshops led by traditional Korean artists, art and photography exhibitions, a Korean song and oratory competition, and Korean fashion displays. Additionally, the Republic of Korea will aid in furnishing the Taekwondo Association of Uzbekistan with sports equipment and will arrange training sessions for athletes from both nations.

In recognition of their contributions to the advancement of Uzbekistan-Korea relations, ten officials from the South Korean government have been honored with the «Dostlik» order.

Korean individuals who have resided in Uzbekistan since the period of deportation in 1937 have significantly contributed to the advancement and growth of their adopted country. Numerous members of the diaspora have been honored with the esteemed distinction of Hero of Labor, including Kim Pen Hwa, the chairman of Polyarnaya Zvezda, who has received this accolade twice. The attainment of independence has ushered in fresh prospects for upholding national

customs, traditions, language, and fostering greater cohesion within the diaspora.

Established in 1991, the Association of Korean Cultural Centers in Uzbekistan operates 23 branches across various regions, including Tashkent city and region, Andijan, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Navoi, Namangan, Syrdarya, Fergana, Khor- ezm regions, and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. These centers serve as hubs where Koreans engage in learning their mother tongue, partake in festivities encompassing both Uzbekistan's national and state holidays and Korean cultural celebrations such as Sollal (Korean New Year), Dano (Summer Festival), and Chuseok (Harvest Festival). [Association of Korean Cultural Centers of Uzbekistan...]

The creative consortium «Arirang» and the literary club Cho Men Hee publish books and compilations about renowned Korean personalities who have resided or currently reside in Uzbekistan, along with works by Korean authors and poets. The Youth Center of the Association organizes the «Compatriots Network» conference, seminars focusing on Korean customs, and actively participates in public gatherings and philanthropic initiatives. Performances by dance troupes like «Koryo,» «Kotbonari,» «Samdiyon,» and «Sy- adal» in various regions of the nation have deeply resonated with audiences.

The enthusiastic involvement of young individuals in the association underscores the flourishing existence of the Korean diaspora, which has been rooted in Uzbekistan for nearly eight decades. The experiences of Koreans in Uzbeki- stan are covered in the newspaper «Koryo Sinmun» and tele- vised through programs like «Chinsen» and «Yagona Oilada» on Uzbekistan's television networks.

Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea have established a

robust alliance founded on cultural and humanitarian collaboration. This partnership has catalyzed a diverse fabric of mutual comprehension, admiration, and advancement. By jointly prioritizing cultural interchange, these nations have nurtured a dynamic relationship that thrives to this day.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan is scheduled to undertake an official state visit to the Republic of Korea from November 22-25, 2017, following an invitation extended by President Moon Jae-in of the Republic of Korea. [Uzbekistan - South Korea..., 2017]

In the field of sport, currently, active exchanges are being conducted in Taekwondo, Kurash. Especially, on June 14, 2024, the two countries signed a “*Cultural Cooperation Memorandum of Understanding*.” [Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism..., Nov. 20, 2024] This includes mutual exchange and cooperation among cultural institutions such as museums and libraries, participation in each country’s cultural events, and expanded collaboration in the field of sports.

Kurash, a sport of Uzbekistan, was officially included in the 2018 Jakarta Asian Games and is set to feature in the 2026 Nagoya Asian Games. Notably, South Korean athletes Kwon Jae-deog and Jeong Jun-young won bronze medals at the 2022 Hangzhou Asian Games. [Kurash Confederation Asia-Oceania..., 2024] Additionally, the Korea Kurash Federation is officially registered with both the Korean Sport & Olympic Committee and the Ministry of Culture, Sports, and Tourism. South Korea currently has 7 male and 7 female national athletes, along with 5 international and 52 national referees registered. (Korea Kurash Federation, n.d.)

Kurash is partly familiar to Korean Judo and Ssireum athletes. Judo, a Japanese sport, involves grappling the oppo-

ment's collar or upper body to throw them down, while Ssireum, a traditional Korean sport, requires gripping a thigh band around the opponent's waist to bring them to the ground. Although Kurash, Judo, and Ssireum each have distinct rules, they share a common feature as grappling sports focused on grabbing and throwing the opponent to the ground. Especially, most Korean Kurash athletes come from Judo backgrounds. [Lee, Jun-Gil, and Chang-Bum Park, 2023]

With Kurash's inclusion in the Asian Games, it is likely that athletes from Ssireum, Judo, and Jiu-Jitsu in South Korea will increasingly participate in the sport. This is expected to expand the international player pool for Kurash, boosting its prominence, especially in preparation for the 2026 Nagoya Asian Games.

Taekwondo, as Korea's traditional martial art, has its roots in ancient times. During the medieval period, specifically Goryeo and the early Joseon Dynasties (10th to 16th centuries), it existed as a martial art known as Subakhee. [Kukkiwon, 2024] This later evolved into Takkyeon, which primarily focused on kicking techniques. Despite hardships during the Japanese colonial period and the Korean War, Taekwondo's legacy continued, leading to the formation of the Korea Taekwondo Association in 1961. During this process, Taekwondo was designated as Korea's national martial art, and in 1971, the World Taekwondo Federation (WTF) was established, with the first World Taekwondo Championships held in Seoul. Taekwondo was then introduced as a demonstration sport in the 1988 Seoul Olympics and officially became an Olympic sport in the 2000 Sydney Olympics. [International Olympic Committee, 2024]

In Uzbekistan, there are two main Taekwondo associa-

tions: the first is the World Taekwondo Federation (WTF), which oversees Olympic Taekwondo, and the other is the International Taekwon-Do Federation (ITF).

The International Taekwon-Do Federation (ITF) was originally founded by Choi Hong Hi within the Korea Taekwondo Association but later separated due to political reasons. Unlike WTF Taekwondo, ITF Taekwondo allows punches to the face and includes more aggressive techniques, contributing to its popularity. [Seong, H., 2015] After the establishment of the WTF, the ITF mainly focused on promoting Taekwondo in socialist countries. In Uzbekistan, there are currently 33 ITF Taekwondo instructors [International Taekwon-Do Federation..., 2024] and approximately 40,000 ITF practitioners. [Khasanov, Laziz, 2020] Additionally, Tashkent hosted the 1st Central Asian ITF Taekwondo Championships in 2023, and the Taekwondo Cup of Uzbekistan Championship in 2018. These events demonstrate the growing popularity of ITF Taekwondo in Uzbekistan.

Meanwhile, the World Taekwondo Federation (WTF) Taekwondo enjoys significant popularity in Uzbekistan, fostering active exchanges with South Korea. Uzbekistan achieved its first Taekwondo gold medal through Ulugbek Rashitov at the Tokyo 2021 Olympic Games and further solidified its success with another gold medal at the 2024 Paris Olympics.

The Embassy of the Republic of Korea in Uzbekistan hosted the Junior Taekwondo Championship on September 6, 2024. This event was supported as part of the K-Silk Road Initiative and was facilitated by the Memorandum of Understanding on Cultural Cooperation signed between South Korea and Uzbekistan on June 14, 2024. [Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, Une 17, 2024]

Master Baek Mun-jong, often referred to as the “Father of Uzbek Taekwondo,” has played a pivotal role in promoting K-Sports within Uzbekistan and across the broader Central Asian region. On May 20, 2024, he organized the 15th Baek Mun-jong Cup International Taekwondo Tournament, which drew participation from 3,500 Dan-certified athletes representing countries such as the United States, South Korea, and members of the CIS, including Kazakhstan and Tajikistan. Dispatched to Uzbekistan in 2009 by the Korea Foundation [MBN, 2009], Master Baek has served as a professor at the Uzbek State University of Physical Culture and Sport. Since his arrival, he has consistently contributed to the development and popularization of Taekwondo in Uzbekistan through the annual organization of international Taekwondo tournaments. Additionally, since 2022, he has been operating a free Taekwondo club at the Korean Education Center in Tashkent, further enhancing the accessibility and growth of the sport. [Lim, J., 2022]

The spread of Taekwondo has led to active interactions with the education and healthcare sectors. Since October 2017, a department of Taekwondo and Sport Activities has been established at the National University of Uzbekistan. Additionally, in the field of medical exchange, the Korea-Uzbekistan Friendship Oriental Medicine Clinic provided acupuncture treatment for injured youth Taekwondo athletes in Uzbekistan in 2009 as part of a volunteer program (Akom News, 2009). [Akom News, 2009]

So far, culture transfer was largely one-directional from Korea to Uzbekistan through Hallyu, Taekwondo, and K-POP, with little awareness of Uzbek culture in Korea.

The introduction of Kurash through the Asian Games pro-

vides a platform for reciprocal cultural exchange, facilitating greater awareness of Uzbek culture in South Korea. As Kurash gains traction in Korea, it has the potential to enhance Uzbekistan's national image and soft power through sports, while simultaneously advancing initiatives such as the K-Silk Road Initiative.

Furthermore, successful athletes can serve as brand ambassadors for sportswear and media outlets, generating economic value and fostering growth within the sports industry. Similar to the role Taekwondo has played in promoting cultural exchange in Uzbekistan—through its integration into university curricula, volunteer programs, and free community clubs—coordinated efforts by both Korea and Uzbekistan to popularize Kurash in Korea could serve as an effective mechanism for disseminating Uzbek culture on a broader scale.

The “Cultural Cooperation Memorandum of Understanding,” signed on June 14, encompasses key initiatives, including support for the Uzbekistan Junior Taekwondo Tournament scheduled for September 2024 and joint training programs for national teams from developing countries, with a focus on 23 athletes in fencing. [Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism. June 17, 2024] Within this framework, integrating traditional Uzbek sports such as Kurash could provide an opportunity to establish a comprehensive joint training system and improve the infrastructure necessary for hosting international tournaments. Moreover, this initiative serves as a platform for promoting Uzbek culture in South Korea, fostering a more balanced and mutually beneficial cultural cooperation agreement.

Additionally, with media coverage, this initiative could increase public awareness and interest in Kurash. Consequent-

ly, it may garner greater public support and financial backing, including corporate and individual sponsorships, for the Korean national Kurash team, further elevating the sport's prominence in Korea.

Meanwhile, the Korean Sport & Olympic Committee conducts joint training programs by inviting athletes from developing countries each year. For Uzbekistan, the national wrestling team was invited to Jincheon National Training Center of Korean Sport and Olympic Committee in 2017 [Jang, H., December 8, 2017], while the national judo team trained with Korean athletes at Yongin University in 2014. [Kim, Juyun, June 8, 2014] Through these invitations, Uzbekistan can adopt Korea's scientific athlete training systems and share advanced training equipment (such as smart gyms and neurofeedback devices) as part of ODA(Official Development Assistance) initiatives. Expanding these invitation programs and increasing the involvement of implementing organizations could enhance the benefits of such exchanges.

On the other hand, Uzbekistan is a global powerhouse in boxing, having won five gold medals in the boxing category at the 2024 Paris Olympics, an unparalleled achievement in the past two decades. [Beacham, Greg, August, 2024] Uzbek boxing is renowned worldwide for its agile footwork, systematic defense, precise techniques, and aggressive style. [Camiel, March 5, 2024]

By bringing Uzbek boxing coaches to Korea to revitalize the sport, it could positively influence public perception of Uzbekistan within Korea. Although Korean boxing experienced a golden era in the 1980s, it lost popularity in the 1990s due to organizational splits and declining interest. [KBS News, 1999] Currently, title matches often feature debuting athletes,

lowering the prestige of the sport. [The Daily Today, June 13, 2019], and it has become difficult to secure sponsors for professional boxing events. [Kim, D., Oct. 19, 2019]

If Korea were to engage in regular exchanges with the Uzbekistan Boxing Federation, hire Uzbek coaches, and adopt their boxing style, it could lead to better performance in international competitions and enhance the positive perception of Uzbekistan in Korea. Regular friendly matches, exchange meetings, and sparring sessions between high-level Uzbek boxers and Korean athletes would not only improve the skills of Korean boxers but also familiarize them with Uzbekistan's systematic training methods, nutrition strategies, and competition readiness against international opponents.

Additionally, in 2018, a Uzbek migrant worker won the amateur boxing championship held in Gangwon Province, South Korea. [Kim, D., Oct. 19, 2019] This example demonstrates that promoting boxing could not only enhance the sport but also foster a more positive perception of Uzbek migrant workers in Korea. It would further contribute to Korea's progress towards embracing greater diversity as it transitions into a multicultural society.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

Culture embodies the essence of humanity, encapsulating thoughts and emotions while fostering mutual connection and communication. As a medium of expression, it manifests through music, dance, art, and sports, reflecting unique forms of human behavior. From the era of the Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic to the present day, Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea have engaged in rich cultural exchanges across various domains, including literature, painting, mu-

sic, dance, sports, and official development assistance. These exchanges have significantly contributed to the evolution of their bilateral relations into a strategic partnership.

A pivotal aspect of this partnership is the role of the Koryosaram, who have served as cultural bridges between the two nations, facilitating mutual understanding and cooperation. By exchanging cultural elements, Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea have not only acknowledged but also celebrated each other's traditions and diversity, fostering profound respect for their distinctive heritages.

This inclusive approach has led to meaningful cultural interactions, enabling deeper connections between their populations. Through a variety of cultural exchange programs and humanitarian initiatives, the two nations have bridged divides and constructed enduring bonds. Sustaining and expanding these interactions is essential for advancing bilateral relations and cultivating a future characterized by enhanced cooperation and mutual prosperity.

The «Cultural Cooperation Memorandum of Understanding,» signed on June 14, 2024, alongside the «K-Silk Road Initiative,» is expected to foster active exchanges in various fields such as art, sports, and tourism. These efforts hold the potential to strengthen Uzbek-Korea relations and enhance bilateral cooperation in the coming years.

Accordingly, the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism of South Korea will host a special exhibition reexamining the past and future of the Silk Road at the National Asia Culture Center in October 2025. In the tourism sector, efforts will focus on promoting medical tourism and educational travel, centering on the Uzbekistan-Tashkent promotional office of the Korea Tourism Organization, which was newly

established in March 2024. Furthermore, the operation of a Korean pavilion at the Tashkent International Tourism Fair in November 2024 will strengthen promotional efforts to attract tourists to Korea. [Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, June 17, 2024]

Despite extensive cultural exchanges between Uzbekistan and South Korea, an imbalance persists, with cultural flows largely one-directional from Korea to Uzbekistan through mediums such as Taekwondo, K-pop, and K-dramas. Conversely, Uzbek culture remains underrepresented in South Korea. Addressing this imbalance is critical to fostering a more reciprocal and equitable cultural partnership. According to this, we suggest these policy recommendations below.

Policy recommendations:

In an increasingly interconnected world, the importance of cultural exchange cannot be overstated. It fosters mutual understanding, respect, and collaboration between nations. This essay outlines key policy recommendations aimed at enhancing cultural relations between Uzbekistan and Korea. By focusing on cultural exchange programs, joint cultural events, and language learning initiatives, these recommendations seek to promote deeper connections and enrich the cultural experiences of both nations.

Enhancing Cultural Exchange Programs

The first policy recommendation emphasizes the enhancement of cultural exchange programs. Supporting youth exchange initiatives is pivotal in engaging students, young artists, and cultural enthusiasts from both Uzbekistan and Korea. Such programs can facilitate firsthand experiences

and interactions that nurture an appreciation for each other's cultural heritage.

In addition to traditional exchanges, the creation of digital cultural platforms is essential. These online resources can host virtual exhibitions and interactive content showcasing the rich cultural narratives of Uzbekistan and Korea. By leveraging technology, cultural exchanges can reach a broader audience, making it accessible to those unable to participate physically.

Scholarship and exchange opportunities are crucial for deepening cultural ties. By providing grants and funding for students, researchers, and cultural professionals, both countries can encourage academic collaboration and cultural immersion. Initiatives supported by organizations like the Korean Foundation, which promotes Korean culture globally, can serve as a model for similar efforts between Uzbekistan and Korea.

Establishing Joint Cultural Events

The second recommendation focuses on organizing joint cultural events. Festivals and cultural performances can serve as vibrant platforms for showcasing the artistic talents of both nations. Culinary experiences, such as food festivals, traditional craft workshops, and film festivals, can highlight the unique cultural offerings of Uzbekistan and Korea, creating opportunities for intercultural dialogue and appreciation.

Furthermore, capacity building and skills development for young artists is essential. Training programs can enhance their artistic skills and promote professional development, allowing for the exchange of innovative ideas and artistic

styles. By supporting the soft power of both countries—such as South Korea's Korean Wave (Hallyu) and Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage from the Silk Road—these initiatives can engage international audiences and foster long-lasting cultural connections.

Supporting Language Learning Initiatives

The third policy recommendation underscores the importance of language learning in promoting cultural understanding. Language serves as a bridge, facilitating communication and preserving cultural heritage. By promoting language exchange programs and providing resources for language learning, both nations can strengthen people-to-people connections.

Facilitating language study abroad programs and utilizing digital platforms for language education can enhance accessibility and engagement. Encouraging language proficiency certifications, like the TOPIK for Korean and the state exams for Uzbek, can further motivate individuals to learn each other's languages, breaking down stereotypes and fostering deeper relationships.

In conclusion, enhancing cultural exchange programs, establishing joint cultural events, and supporting language learning initiatives are vital steps toward strengthening the cultural ties between Uzbekistan and Korea. These policy recommendations not only aim to enrich the cultural experiences of both nations but also foster mutual respect and understanding in an increasingly globalized world. By investing in these areas, Uzbekistan and Korea can cultivate a vibrant cultural dialogue that benefits both societies, paving the way for a future of collaboration and shared cultural enrichment.

1. Sport as a Medium for Cultural Exchange:

To this end, introducing Uzbek culture through sports, such as Kurash, at international events like the Asian Games presents a unique opportunity for mutual cultural exchange. This initiative not only raises awareness of Uzbek traditions in South Korea but also strengthens mutual understanding while fostering socio-economic interactions and creating a more balanced cultural framework.

2. Digital Platforms for Cultural Promotion:

Promoting Uzbek culture in South Korea requires enhanced digital platforms, such as internet communities and mobile applications, to connect Uzbeks and Koreans. Increasing the number of Central Asia-themed events in South Korea can further highlight Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage, including iconic tourist destinations like Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva. Experiences such as Uzbek culinary traditions, traditional clothing, housing culture, and music could significantly enrich Korean society's appreciation of Uzbek culture.

3. Establishing an Uzbek Cultural Center:

Countries like the United States, the United Kingdom and Saudi Arabia actively promote their cultures in South Korea through embassy-operated cultural centers. Following this model, the Embassy of Uzbekistan in Korea could establish a dedicated cultural center to host regular events such as language exchange programs, culinary workshops, and exhibitions. These initiatives could play a vital role in increasing the visibility and influence of Uzbek culture in South Korea.

4. Empowering the Koryo-saram Community:

The Koryo-saram community, residing in Central Asia for nearly a century and concentrated largely in Uzbekistan, possesses a dual identity rooted in a deep understanding of Uzbek society and cultural ties to Korea. This unique position makes them invaluable as cultural ambassadors between the two nations. Vocational training programs for Koryo-saram—focused on teaching Korean language and culture, guiding Uzbek tourism, and providing interpretation in Russian and Uzbek—can empower them to actively contribute to bilateral cultural exchange. Their efforts could serve as a key pathway for introducing Uzbek culture to Korea and fostering deeper connections between the two countries.

By addressing these imbalances and implementing the proposed initiatives, Uzbekistan and South Korea can significantly enhance their cultural partnership, fostering a more balanced exchange that aligns with their broader strategic objectives.

Since the establishment of a «strategic partnership» in 2006, relations between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea were further elevated in 2019 to a «special strategic partnership.» These ties have been reinforced through the *K-Silk Road Initiative*, which seeks to promote socio-economic cooperation between South Korea and Central Asian countries. This initiative emphasizes collaboration in key sectors such as mineral and gas resources, culture, and development assistance. Within this framework, cultural exchange plays a pivotal role in fostering public support and mutual understanding of the initiative's goals. By actively advancing cultural exchanges, the bilateral relationship be-

tween Uzbekistan and South Korea can continue to evolve, contributing to sustained collaboration and mutual prosperity.

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ABOUT KOREAN EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: PAST AND PRESENT

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Abstract. The study deals with the history of Korean education in Uzbekistan, covering the Soviet period and the following years of independence. It examines the historical evolution of Korean language learning in schools and higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, the formation of Korean language organizations and courses in the region, and the establishment of South Korean university branches in Tashkent and other cities. The paper provides statistics regarding Uzbek youth studying in South Korea and analyzes the factors influencing applicants' selection of Korean universities.

Key words: Uzbekistan, education, Korean language, South Korean universities

Currently, there is a growing discourse over the concept of “soft power” in contemporary society. The primary conflicts occur not on traditional battlefields but within the realms of the Internet and social media, encompassing information, values, worldviews, and the perception of “friend or foe” among other aspects. Undoubtedly, education is significantly influential in this context, serving as a form of *soft power* through which various nations disseminate their accomplishments in culture, science, and technology, alongside the ideals and norms inherent to their social frameworks; numerous states incorporate it effectively into their foreign policy framework and strategy. Acknowledging the growing significance of universities within the

global space, modern-day countries are actively competing for talented and committed candidates.

Korean institutions are consistently listed among the top 100 in the world's most respected rankings, strengthening their status in the international arena. Annually, thousands of Uzbek students are attracted to universities throughout the peninsula as Korean educational programs continue to gain popularity. Despite the growing recognition of Korean universities and language institutes among Uzbek youth, the study of the Korean language in Uzbekistan has a long history. Thus, Korean education in Uzbekistan can be divided into three categories: (1) Korean education in Uzbekistan during the Soviet era, which mainly involves the preservation of the Korean language and culture among the Koryo-saram, who were deported by Stalin from the Far East in 1937; (2) the opening of branches of Korean universities and other educational institutions in Uzbekistan following independence; and (3) education of Uzbekistani youth in educational institutions in South Korea.

Korean Education in Uzbekistan during the Soviet era. The history of Korean Enlightenment in Uzbekistan began after the deportation of the Koreans from the Far East to Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan in 1937. Archival data indicates that at the beginning of 1938-39, there were 96 Korean schools, with 44 Korean schools and 52 mixed Korean schools in the region (Rahmankulova, 2010). Nevertheless, Korean schools have a rather short history since all national schools, including those for Koreans, were required to be reformed into standardized Soviet schools with Russian as the primary language of instruction. The transformation of Korean schools into Soviet-style schools occurred between 1939 and 1940 (Khan, 2014, p. 63).

In the second half of the 1940s, the teaching Korean language resumed in the country. Korean language was taught instead of Uzbek in 3-10th grades for an average of two hours weekly, mainly in schools—primarily located at Korean collective farms—with a prevailing number of Korean children. Even in the 1970s and 1980s, the majority of students on Korean collective farms were Koryo-saram children. Korean language was taught not only in Tashkent but also in the Samarkand and Khorezm regions. During that period, a range of textbooks and teaching materials were developed, and the first republican symposium for Korean language instructors was held in Uzbekistan in 1954. (Hegay, 1991, p. 258-259). In the first half of 1960, a Korean language textbook for 3-4th grades was produced; in 1965, a new Korean language curriculum for 3-11th grades and a textbook for 3-4th grades were released (Hegay, 1991, p. 260).

An important training on Korean language took place in 1956 with the opening of the Department of Korean Language and Literature at the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute named after Nizami; it was created by the efforts of candidates of philological sciences Hwang Yun Dune and Hegai Alexei, as well as a graduate of the Leningrad Institute of Oriental Studies, Kan Vladimir. Kim Byung-soo became the head of the department. Ho Um Bae, a citizen of the DPRK, also worked at the department (Khan, 2014, p. 64). The first class (1961) consisted of 15 people. In total, 4 classes of 70 people were carried out; the department existed until 1964 and was reopened in 1985 (Li, 2006).

Following the independence, the Department of Korean Studies was established at the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies (TashGIV) in 1993, with a former citizen of the DPRK, Kim Moon Uk (candidate of chemical sciences), as

the first head; later the position in charge was taken by Kim Victoria. Since 2012, TashGIV has been hosting an intellectual quiz competition for knowledge of the Korean language, which is attended by applicants from various universities and colleges in Uzbekistan (Khan, 2014, p. 116).

Korean language educational institutions in Uzbekistan. In May 1992, the Educational Center at the Embassy of the Republic of Korea in Uzbekistan was opened and rapidly attained popularity among both Korean and non-Korean students. A total of 100,000 students has received training in Korean language during this initiative. Currently, around 3,580 people are registered in 52 groups at the center. Furthermore, students are welcome to participate in K-POP, traditional dance, and drumming workshops (Kim, 2022). Another popular South Korean organization providing training in Korean language is Sejong Hakdang (King Sejong Institute); it is officially accredited by the Korean government. In addition to Korean language classes, the center organizes different festivals and competitions, as well as major events celebrated in South Korea, encouraging students to get familiar with Korean traditions. A few years ago almost all the students were of Koryo-saram heritage, but now about 40% are ethnic Uzbeks, drawn by a fascination with Korean music and film, or the allure of emigrating to South Korea for work or education (Casey, 2024). In 2021, the Sejong Haktang 2 was opened at Inha University in Tashkent and initiated an internship program in Korea for outstanding students, entirely funded by the King Sejong Foundation.

Today, Korean is one of the most popular foreign languages in Uzbekistan. It is taught in 14 universities in Uzbekistan: Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, Tashkent

State Institute of Oriental Studies, Uzbek State University of World Languages, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Nukus, Urgench, Namangan Universities, Angren Regional Pedagogical Institute, Bucheon University in Tashkent, etc. Moreover, more than 100 centers and courses are offering Korean language classes, including schools, colleges, and courses at Korean cultural centers, with approximately 10,000 individuals enrolled in total. The popularity of Korean language has led to an increasing number of tutors who advertise their classes in newspapers, websites, or social media. However, not all of them are certified teachers; some of them are students, while others are people who have spent some time in Korea and have basic language communication skills. Besides language courses, information about Korean language, history, and culture can be found on the pages of the “Koryo Sinmun” newspaper and the “Chinsen” program on state television.

Branches of Korean universities in Uzbekistan. At the moment, Uzbekistan and South Korea are actively developing their relations in all areas, with a particular emphasis on trade and economic collaboration, which is also impacting the field of Korean language education. Thus, a few years ago, language study predominantly served the purpose of communication—the demand for Korean language translators at all proficiency levels has been notably high. Nowadays, proficiency in Korean has become an essential skill for succeeding in modern careers. Merely having the ability to express oneself in the language is insufficient; a high level of competence is essential for professional development. Over the past decade, several branches of Korean universi-

ties have initiated educational programs in Uzbekistan, a phenomenon that is rather unusual within the post-Soviet space. At present, there are 5 branches of Korean universities in Uzbekistan:

- 1) Inha University (IUT) in Tashkent was founded in 2014 and established in cooperation with Inha University (Republic of Korea). It is the first international branch of Korean university in the world.
- 2) Bucheon University (BUT) in Tashkent was founded in 2018 under the initiative of the Ministry of Preschool Education, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and Bucheon University (Republic of Korea).
- 3) Kimyo International University (KIUT) in Tashkent was originally established under the name of Yeosu Technical Institute in 2018. Currently, KIUT provides training in 29 undergraduate majors and 20 master's specialties and has branches in Namangan and Samarkand.
- 4) Ajou University (AUT) in Tashkent was founded in 2020 in cooperation with Ajou University (Republic of Korea).
- 5) The Korean International University (KIUF) in Ferghana was founded in 2019.

Inha University trains specialists in information and communication technologies, business, and logistics. Bucheon University has departments of preschool education, Korean language and management, architecture, nutrition, information technology, multimedia and game content, and electronic business. Ajou University offers training in 3 major disciplines: architecture, construction engineering, and electrical and computer engineering. The opening of these branches was driven by the need and

demand for Korean education; for instance, Inha University has about 1,500 enrolled students, whereas Bucheon University has 1,200.

The universities of Bucheon and Kimyo provide 2+2 or 3+1 programs, depending on the faculty. These universities offer good opportunities for students to pursue further studies in South Korea through exchange programs at Hanyang University, Chungbuk National University, Chosun University, Busan University of Foreign Studies, Jeonju University, and Chungcheong University, among others. Inha University in Tashkent grants an opportunity for 10 excellent and motivated students to attend the Inha University Summer School in Korea at no expense. Many students choose Korean university branches precisely to pursue their education in Korea—they study Korean before entering the university, which is considered necessary to acquire the desired profession.

Uzbekistani Students in Korea. Before the pandemic, the overall number of international students in South Korea was 143,000. In 2020, it decreased to 137,000 but began rising again when the limitations on travel were lifted. In 2023, the total of international students has reached 188,000 people, encompassing students in bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programs, as well as those engaged in language courses and internships (Lee, 2023). The same year, the Korean government announced a strategy to attract 300,000 foreign students to Korea, designed to address the challenges faced by provincial universities and regions, which are experiencing a decline due to the country's low birth rate and the migration of local youth to larger urban areas. In 2024, the overall number surpassed 200,000 for the first time, reaching 208,962 individuals. Relative to 2022, it is a

significant increase of 25%, and in comparison to 2023 (181,842 individuals) of 15% growth (27,120 individuals) (Lee, 2024). The distribution of foreign students by country of citizenship is as follows: China (34.5%), Vietnam (26.8%), Mongolia (5.9%), and Uzbekistan (5.8%). Particularly in case of Uzbek learners, the number increased from 2,667 in 2017 to 8,164 in 2021, representing about a threefold rise (Jang, Lee, Nam, & Park, 2022, p. 90); Uzbekistan has secured a spot in the top 5 countries with the highest number of foreign students in South Korea, according to a recent report by Yonhap news agency (Daryo, 2024; Park, 2024). The sustained influx of Uzbek learners is caused not only by established diplomatic connections between Korea and Uzbekistan but by the global spread of the Korean Wave, Korea's cultural appeal, particularly the popularity of K-pop and K-dramas, and the growing interest in learning Korean language for prospective employment opportunities. As the current trend anticipates a steady increase in the number of Uzbek learners residing in Korea in the future, there is a significant number of websites, both Uzbek and Korean, about educational opportunities, including scholarship programs. The Korean Government Scholarship is the most sought-after, offering funding for master's and doctoral degrees, or short-term scientific internships ranging from six months to one year. This program fully covers tuition, housing, and health insurance expenses.

According to statistics from the Ministry of Education of Korea dated 2024.10.28, 1,138 people from Uzbekistan are enrolled in language courses. The bachelor's degree program has 5,542 students in the humanities, 2,039 in engineering, 487 in natural sciences, 288 in entertainment and sports, and none in medicine. The master's programs include 1624 students in humanities faculties, 273 in engineering, 23 in

natural science, 34 in entertainment and sports, and 2 in medical faculties. Doctoral programs include 310 students in the humanities, 55 in engineering, 13 in natural science, 5 in entertainment and sports, and 3 in medical colleges. In 2024, the total number of students from Uzbekistan reached 12,025: language courses – 1,138, Bachelor – 8,356, Master – 1,956, Doctorate – 386, other programs – 189 (Korean Ministry of Education, 2024).

Conclusion. The further development of Uzbek-Korean relations in educational sector needs to advance with an awareness of the significance of soft power in the today's geopolitical landscape. Uzbekistan hosts 1 branch each of American, British, Italian, Singaporean, and Indian universities, alongside 4 branches from Korean institutions, and 14 Russian university branches. In South Korea, a total of 12,025 Uzbekistani students are currently undergoing training, while in Russia, more than 500 institutions in 140 cities have registered 63,000 students in 2024. In the context of the youth destined to become the future elite of Uzbekistan, the relevant question arises: which university graduates will form this group?

In this case, suggestions for enhancing Korean-Uzbek relations in the areas of education, science, and culture, considering the growing significance of soft power—particularly amid the confrontation between the Global West and the Global South—are as follows:

- a) Expansion of Korean university branches in Uzbekistan;
- b) Reduction in tuition fees in comparison to branches of other foreign universities;

- c) Increase of the variety of majors;
- d) Expansion of master's and doctoral programs;
- e) Improvement of chances for obtaining an education in Korea itself (in addition to the existing opportunities).

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SPORTS EXCHANGES AND SPORTS ODA BETWEEN KOREA AND UZBEKISTAN

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1. Introduction

The Paralympic crowd, Olympic Stadium
[Sones, 2012]

With the combination of global media and sports, sports have adopted elements of transnationalism, leading to the

reproduction of cross-cultural, ideological, and emotional exchanges. In particular, nationalism and transnationalism coexist in sports. In the Olympic Games, sports serve as a platform for expanding inter-state exchanges and cooperation, as well as for increasing international economic and business spaces, thereby enhancing the multi-dimensional aspects of transnationalism. In other words, the Olympic phenomenon acts as a transnational public arena that exerts political, economic, and cultural influence beyond nations. [Yoo, 2019]

As an intangible yet semi-concrete entity, the state reinforces its imagined existence and visibility through the collective physical competition of sports. At the same time, individuals project their self-identity onto national athletes and their respective sports, thereby expanding their personal identity through a process of alignment. This phenomenon, when combined with media, reshapes the world into a virtual reality. Through television and the internet, stadiums become spaces of uniform rules, reflecting the spirit of equal international competition and global participation.

However, a significant asymmetry exists in cultural exchange between Korea and Uzbekistan. While Korean culture exerts a profound influence in Uzbekistan, Uzbek culture remains relatively unknown in Korea. This imbalance raises concerns about neo-cultural imperialism, manifesting in cultural dependency, a lack of mutual understanding, and cultural marginalization.

Existing research on Korea-Uzbekistan cultural exchanges has predominantly focused on the global popularity of Hal-

lyu, K-POP, and music-related interactions. However, studies on sports exchanges remain exceedingly limited. This gap underscores the need to explore sports as a novel and effective medium for fostering balanced and reciprocal cultural exchanges.

Sports, guided by the universal principle of sportsmanship, have a unique capacity to unite people across physical and cultural boundaries. In the digital age, this unity extends to virtual spaces through shared activities, such as watching broadcasts and engaging in online discussions. These shared experiences create a «public square» where diverse perspectives converge, fostering meaningful cross-cultural dialogue within a transnational framework. In this way, sports transcend their traditional role, becoming a powerful mechanism for advancing international collaboration and cultural exchange.

This paper seeks to address the blind spots in Korea-Uzbekistan cultural exchanges by emphasizing the untapped potential of sports. It will examine the historical context of sports interactions between the two nations, highlight specific cases such as Kurash, Taekwondo, and Boxing, and propose strategies for leveraging sports diplomacy to promote more equitable and culturally enriching exchanges.

2. Recent Korea-Uzbekistan Sports Exchange Cases

Yonhap News. (2024, June 15). *President Yoon: «Toward the future with Uzbekistan,» Mirziyoyev: «A close friend»* [Photograph]. Provided by Korea International Trade Association. Retrieved from https://www.kita.net/board/totalTradeNews/totalTradeNewsDetail.do;jsessionid_KITA=FE9C9E7C423276291A5F4FCC8F2735D8.Hyper?no=84344&siteId=1

Currently, active exchanges are being conducted in Taekwondo, Kurash, and soccer. Notably, on June 14, 2024, the two countries signed a “Cultural Cooperation Memorandum of Understanding.” This agreement includes mutual exchange and cooperation among cultural institutions such as museums and libraries, participation in each country’s cultural events, and expanded collaboration in the field of sports.

1) Case 1: Kurash

Kurash, meaning “reaching the goal in a just or fair way,” is a traditional wrestling sport of Uzbekistan with a history spanning over 3,000 years. In 1992, under the initiative of

Uzbekistan's former President Islam Karimov, efforts began to transform Kurash into an international sport. Since then, international Kurash forums have been held in countries like South Korea, Canada, Japan, India, and the United States, culminating in the first International Kurash Federation tournament held in Tashkent in 1999. [International Kurash Association. n.d.]

Following its successful internationalization, Kurash was officially included in the 2018 Jakarta Asian Games and is set to feature in the 2026 Nagoya Asian Games. Notably, South Korean athletes Kwon Jae-deog and Jeong Jun-young won bronze medals at the 2022 Hangzhou Asian Games.

Lee, J. H. (2022, November 29). *Republic of Korea Kurash National Team achieves overall 3rd place at the 13th World Championships* [Photograph]. *Jungbu Maeil*. Retrieved from <https://www.jbnews.com/news/articleView.html?idxno=1377676>

Additionally, the Korea Kurash Federation is officially registered with both the Korean Sport & Olympic Committee and the Ministry of Culture, Sports, and Tourism. South Korea currently has 7 male and 7 female national athletes, along with 5 international and 52 national referees registered. [Korea Kurash Federation, n.d.]

Kurash (Uzbekistan) [Wikipedia Commons, 2022]

Ssireum (Korea)

Judo (Japan)

[Wikipedia Commons, 2019]

Kurash Games in South Korea

Year	Name [Korea Kurash Federation, n.d.]
2024	The Korea Kurash Federation President's Cup & 2024 National Team Final Selection Tournament
2023	1. National Amateur Kurash Championship & Busan Kurash Federation President's Cup 2. National Kurash Championship & 2024 National Team First Selection Tournament 3. Korea Kurash Federation President's Cup & Hangzhou Asian Games National Team Final Selection Tournament (Third Round) 4. 16th National Martial Arts Festival Kurash Championship (Minister of Culture, Sports, and Tourism Award)
2021	2021 Kurash and Wushu Tournament & Online World Martial Arts Masterships National Team Selection (Hosted by Cheongju Kurash Federation)
2019	2019 Chungju World Martial Arts Masterships & 12th World Kurash Championship
2018	2018 Busan World Beach Kurash Championship

Kurash is somewhat familiar to Korean judo and Ssireum athletes. Judo, a Japanese sport, involves grappling the opponent's collar or upper body to throw them down, while Ssireum, a traditional Korean sport, requires gripping a thigh band around the opponent's waist to bring them to the ground. Although Kurash, Judo, and Ssireum have distinct rules, they share a common feature as grappling sports focused on grabbing and throwing the opponent to the ground. Notably, most Korean Kurash athletes come from judo backgrounds. [Lee & Park, 2023]

With Kurash's inclusion in the Asian Games, it is likely that athletes from Ssireum, Judo, and Jiu-Jitsu in South Korea will increasingly participate in the sport. This is expected to expand the international player pool for Kurash and boost its

prominence, particularly in preparation for the 2026 Nagoya Asian Games.

2) Case 2: Taekwondo

Taekwondo, as Korea's traditional martial art, has its roots in ancient times. During the medieval period, specifically Goryeo and the early Joseon Dynasties (10th to 16th centuries), it existed as a martial art known as Subakhee. [Kukkiwon, 2024] This later evolved into Takkyeon, which primarily focused on kicking techniques. Despite hardships during the Japanese colonial period and the Korean War, Taekwondo's legacy continued, leading to the formation of the Korea Taekwondo Association in 1961. [Korea Taekwondo Association, n.d.] During this process, Taekwondo was designated as Korea's national martial art, and in 1971, the World Taekwondo Federation (WTF) was established, with the first World Taekwondo Championships held in Seoul. Taekwondo was then introduced as a demonstration sport in the 1988 Seoul Olympics and officially became an Olympic sport in the 2000 Sydney Olympics. [International Olympic Committee, n.d.]

In Uzbekistan, there are two main Taekwondo associations: the first is the World Taekwondo Federation (WTF), which oversees Olympic Taekwondo, and the other is the International Taekwon-Do Federation (ITF).

The ITF was originally founded by Choi Hong Hi within the Korea Taekwondo Association but later separated due to political reasons. Unlike WTF Taekwondo, ITF Taekwondo allows punches to the face and includes more aggressive techniques, contributing to its popularity. [Seong, 2015] After the establishment of the WTF, the ITF mainly focused on promot-

ing Taekwondo in socialist countries. In Uzbekistan, there are currently 33 ITF Taekwondo instructors [International Taekwon-Do Federation, n.d.] and approximately 40,000 ITF practitioners. [Khasanov, 2020] Additionally, Tashkent hosted the 1st Central Asian ITF Taekwon-Do Championships in 2023, and the Taekwondo Cup of Uzbekistan Championship in 2018. These events demonstrate the growing popularity of ITF Taekwondo in Uzbekistan.

Meanwhile, World Taekwondo Federation (WTF) Taekwondo is also highly popular in Uzbekistan, with active exchanges taking place with South Korea. At the Tokyo 2021 Olympic Games, Uzbekistan secured its first Taekwondo gold medal through Ulugbek Rashitov and achieved further success on gold medal at the 2024 Paris Olympics

The Embassy of the Republic of Korea in Uzbekistan hosted the Junior Taekwondo Championship on September 6, 2024. This event was supported as part of the K-Silk Road Initiative and was facilitated by the Memorandum of Understanding on Cultural Cooperation signed between South Korea and Uzbekistan on June 14, 2024. [Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism of the Republic of Korea, 2024]

And Master Baek Mun-jong, widely recognized as the «Father of Uzbek Taekwondo» organized the 15th Baek Mun-jong Cup International Taekwondo Tournament on May 20, 2024, actively promoting K-Sports throughout Uzbekistan and the broader Central Asian region. This competition attracted 3,500 athletes with Dan certificates from various countries, including the United States, South Korea, and CIS states such as Kazakhstan and Tajikistan. Dispatched to Uzbekistan in 2009 through the Korea Foundation, [MBN, 2009]

Park, J. (2024, May 22). *[Photo news] 15th Dr. Baek Moon-jong Cup International Taekwondo Tournament [Photograph]. Finance Today*. Retrieved from

<https://www.fntoday.co.kr/news/articleView.html?idxno=321126>

Master Baek has been serving as a professor at the Uzbek State University of Physical Culture and Sport. Since his arrival, he has consistently organized international Taekwondo tournaments on an annual basis, significantly contributing to the development and popularization of Taekwondo in Uzbekistan. And he has been running a free Taekwondo club from 2022 at the Korean Education Center in Tashkent. [Lim, 2022]

The spread of Taekwondo has led to active interactions with the education and healthcare sectors. Since October 2017, a department of Taekwondo and Sport Activities has been established at the National University of Uzbekistan.

Additionally, in the field of medical exchange, the Korea-Uzbekistan Friendship Oriental Medicine Clinic provided acupuncture treatment for injured youth Taekwondo athletes in Uzbekistan in 2009 as part of a volunteer program. [Akom News, 2009]

3) Case 3. Boxing

Uzbekistan is recognized as a global powerhouse in boxing, achieving an unprecedented milestone by securing five gold medals in boxing at the 2024 Paris Olympics—an unparalleled accomplishment in the past two decades. Uzbek boxing is internationally acclaimed for its agile footwork, structured defensive strategies, precise technical execution, and dynamic, aggressive approach.

In contrast, Korean boxing experienced a golden era in the 1980s but lost popularity in the 1990s due to organizational splits and a decline in public interest. [KBS News, 1999] Currently, title matches often feature debuting athletes, lowering the prestige of the sport, and it has become difficult to secure sponsors for professional boxing events. [The Daily Today, 2019]

Facilitating boxing exchanges, such as sending Uzbek coaches to Korea and organizing matches to introduce unique Uzbek techniques, could revitalize Korean boxing while improving perceptions of Uzbekistan in Korea.

Lee, K. (2018, November 26). *Uzbek migrant worker wins provincial amateur boxing competition* [Photograph]. *The Sorak Weekly News*. Retrieved from <http://www.soraknews.co.kr/detail.php?number=10447>

In 2018, Nomuratov Zafar, an Uzbek migrant worker won the amateur boxing championship held in Gangwon Province, South Korea. [Lee, 2018] Boxing collaborations between Korea and Uzbekistan have the potential to enhance multicultural sportsmanship while contributing to a more nuanced and favorable perception of Uzbek migrant workers in Korea. By encouraging their participation in social events, such initiatives could further support Korea's prog-

ress toward embracing greater diversity as it transitions into a multicultural society.

3. Sports ODA (Official Development Assistance) between Korea and Uzbekistan

The Korean Sport & Olympic Committee organizes joint training programs annually by inviting athletes from developing countries.

Yonhap News. (2017, December 8). *Korean Sport & Olympic Committee invites athletes from Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Cambodia to Jincheon National Training Center* [Photograph]. *Yonhap News*. Retrieved from <https://www.yna.co.kr/view/AKR20171208084900007>

In 2017, the Uzbek national wrestling team was invited to the Jincheon National Training Center operated by the Korean Sport & Olympic Committee. Similarly, in 2014, the

Uzbek national judo team trained alongside Korean athletes at Yongin University.

Year	Athlete Exchange Program [Korea Sport & Olympic Committee, 2013-2024]
2013	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The "Dream Together" initiative was launched, offering training opportunities to athletes worldwide.
2014	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Uzbek wrestling team trained at Jincheon National Training Center, • The judo team collaborated with Korean athletes at Yongin University. [Kim, 2014]
2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Athletes from Kazakhstan (ice hockey, triathlon), Uzbekistan (wrestling), and Kyrgyzstan (triathlon, modern pentathlon, judo) participated in joint training programs.
2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 230 athletes from 8 countries participated across 13 sports disciplines. • Kyrgyzstan earned three bronze medals at the World Wrestling Championships.
2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 269 athletes from 25 countries participated across 16 sports disciplines, showing significant program growth.

The sports coaching education program for developing countries also aims to cultivate local international coaches. In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the first online international coaching certification courses for triathlon were introduced in 2021, accredited by international federations. That year, the program supported 142 participants from 48 countries across three disciplines. Additionally, from August to November 2021, an online triathlon course was conducted. In Central Asia, Taekwondo coaches from Uzbekistan and cycling coaches from Kyrgyzstan participated in offline training sessions.

Year	Coach Exchange Program [Korea Sport & Olympic Committee, 2022-2024]
2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first online coaching certification courses for triathlon were introduced, with 142 participants from 48 countries. • An online triathlon course was held (August-November) • Offline training involved Taekwondo coaches from Uzbekistan and cycling coaches from Kyrgyzstan."
2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coach Kim Je-cheon was dispatched to Kazakhstan to develop archery skills. • Programs were monitored via reports and satisfaction surveys.
2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coach Kim Myeong-seon has been dispatched, supporting the Uzbek national archery team, participating the Hyundai Archery World Cup.

4. Sports ODA in the Perspective of Merging with AI Technology

Park, T. (2016, August 16). [Interesting science] Behind Korea's archery '10·10·10' was neurofeedback [Photograph]. The Chosun Ilbo. Retrieved from https://newsteacher.chosun.com/site/data/html_dir/2016/08/15/2016081501918.html

In the era of AI, sports ODA must transcend traditional approaches by leveraging advanced technologies to implement innovative and scientific solutions in recipient countries. For instance, South Korea employed “Neuro Feedback” technology during the 2016 Rio Olympics to analyze archery athletes’ brain waves, helping them train their psychological responses under match conditions. In fencing, 3D motion capture technology was used to analyze joint movements precisely, identifying areas for improvement. [Park, 2016]

AI technologies are transforming various sports disciplines, opening new horizons for innovation. For example, IBM annually introduces groundbreaking advancements at the Masters Tournament, one of golf’s four major championships (PGA). In 2024, it launched the “Hole Insights” service, powered by its generative AI platform, Watsonx, providing data analysis and predictive insights for each hole on the course. [Jang, 2024] Similarly, the application of AI technologies in other sports has the potential to revolutionize training and coaching systems, enabling more effective strategies and significant improvements in performance.

South Korea’s leadership in AI is also notable, ranking sixth in the AI Readiness Index among 83 countries worldwide. [Tortoise Media, 2024] In comparison, Uzbekistan ranks 131st, according to the IMF’s 2023 AI Preparedness Index. [Nakispekova, 2024] These rankings highlight the need for AI-based ODA collaboration between South Korea and Central Asian countries.

Leveraging its advanced AI capabilities, South Korea could develop tools to enhance athletic performance, integrate these tools into sports ODA initiatives, and share them with

Central Asia. Such efforts would strengthen the competitive capabilities of Central Asian nations while promoting mutual development through sports exchanges within the framework of the K-Silk Road Initiative.

Expanding AI-powered sports ODA to include not only professional athletes but also the general population in recipient countries could yield broader benefits. By analyzing health conditions and disease prevalence, tailored sports ODA projects could be implemented to foster greater sports participation, improve public health, and contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

5. Conclusion

Cultural exchange between Korea and Uzbekistan has largely been one-sided, with Korean culture introduced to Uzbekistan through Hallyu, Taekwondo, and K-POP, while Uzbek culture remains relatively unknown in Korea. The inclusion of Kurash in the Asian Games presents a unique opportunity to address this imbalance. If Kurash gains popularity in Korea, it could not only enhance Uzbekistan's national image and soft power through sports but also serve as a platform to promote broader initiatives like the K-Silk Road Initiative. Successful athletes could act as ambassadors for Uzbek culture, facilitating sponsorships and collaboration with Korean brands.

Similar to how Taekwondo has integrated into Uzbekistan's cultural landscape, efforts to popularize Kurash in Korea could foster reciprocal cultural exchange. Joint training programs, infrastructure development for tournaments, and the incorporation of Kurash into existing sports curricula could strengthen cultural ties. Promoting Kurash alongside

established sports like Taekwondo and fencing would ensure sustainable, balanced cooperation.

Media coverage will be key in raising public awareness, attracting sponsorships for the Korean national team, and increasing the sport's visibility. Additionally, expanding sports ODA under programs like those by the Korean Sport & Olympic Committee could provide a foundation for deeper sports exchanges. Collaborating with public institutions such as KOICA and NGOs to broaden the scope and budget of sports ODA would ensure the continued success of these initiatives. By enhancing training programs and increasing the number of sports-related candidates in KOICA's volunteer selection process, more fruitful exchanges can be achieved, benefiting both countries in the long term.

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